

CASTING LOTS

FROM A PERSPECTIVE OF GAME STUDIES

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Gewidmet meinem Vater,

der sein Leben dem interkulturellen Austausch performativer, oraler, literaler, und multimedialer Poesie widmete, sowie einen Namen schuf, der der stetigen Selbstbestimmung eigener Identität, Ideen und Ideale verpflichtet ist, und mir weitergab, Ide.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

#lot-casting, #cleromancy, #divination, #chance, #random #gamestudies, #religion #play

This thesis maps the cultivation of chance by analyzing the practice of casting lots as a cultural technique from the perspective of game studies. A “lot” is commonly understood as a random decision maker like a coin-flip or drawing the short end of a stick as in a simple “lottery”. According to Roger Caillois, humans uniquely play with chance (ALEA), while his other play categories of competition (AGÔN), pretending (MIMICRY) and intoxication (ILINX) are also observed among animals.

This thesis questions the academic status quo that the original use of casting lots evolved from divination practices called “cleromancy”. Instead, this thesis argues that an ‘aleatory culture’ using numerals preceded the development of scripture. The thesis first analyses the characteristics of play, divination and decision making, then the physical and performative qualities of objects used as lots and lastly presents a historical analysis what „objects of thought“ (Hacking) concerning ideas of chance have been presented in ancient literature.

Humanity’s oldest written myths already describe the highest Gods casting lots to divide the universe, without having any control over chance nor fate. Instead, this represented common Mesopotamian inheritance law for division of property. Through a playful and seemingly useless process of “casting without aim” or “shaking a quiver” of arrows, we learned to generate quantitative outcomes (Salen & Zimmerman) for random selection or distribution by an unbiased source. Linking chance to fairness enabled to forge strong communal trust, while the „ SACRED EARNEST” (Huizinga) to honor and uphold rules had the casting of lots evolve into cultural institutions that were eventually attributed divine powers.

The Greek word for lot “κλήροϛ“ is also the etymological root of “cleric”. A media revolution of trust in scripture had brought forth new literate theological elites who labeled all unwanted pagan practices as divination, especially concerning conscious randomization. “Cleromancy” would since remain common terminology, in need of revision.

Use of A.I. - Disclaimer

This disclaimer was written in conjunction with the AI-based tool, ChatGPT-4 to have us both reflect its primary uses over the past months. Following this page, the thesis itself is entirely my own work, written in my own words, based on my independent thoughts and deductions. The only other direct AI assistance in the final document was used for the literature list at the end of this thesis to:

- **Format reference lists in APA 7 style.**

The research assistance of ChatGPT-4 became more frequent during the later stages of developing this thesis. While I had begun my research on this topic roughly a year earlier, I was initially reluctant and highly skeptical of AI's reliability in academic work. However, as a Large Language Model (LLM) it had ultimately become an invaluable tool for:

- **Tracing word origins and historical usage**, helping to pinpoint the first known occurrences of specific terms like “cleromancy” across different languages.
- **Exploring etymological roots, synonyms, and linguistic connections**, such as identifying where the term “lot” carries meanings related to “share” or “fate” across various languages.
- **Comparing translations and identifying phrase parallels**, particularly when analyzing variations of religious texts and their original wordings.
- **Compiling contextual information**, such as examining how frequently “casting lots” was used for land division, sortition, or other practices, and assessing whether certain themes were central or marginal in each literary corpus.
- **Locating possible counterarguments**, especially regarding the use of divination.

All information retrieved from AI was critically examined, as ChatGPT-4 often generated responses aligned to please my seeking of answers, while also reflecting prevalent public opinion and dominant scholarly views, that chance had developed out of divination methods. Views I had tried to specifically counter and aimed to falsify. In this regard, it functioned as an intellectual sparring partner rather than a source of knowledge.

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INTRODUCTION

Since the origin of games of chance is academically described as a divinatory practice, my research had started with an interest in the interconnection of play and religious thought by randomly searching influential religious scriptures for the words “play”, “game”, “luck”, “dice” or “gambling” to look for a common pattern. But while in the Hindu realm divine play is a cosmic concept and its vast mythological literature feature dice games and gambling in abundance - ranging from caution to praise - I was disappointed by the scarce results within the Abrahamic holy books, except for some condemnations in the Qur'an. But when pointed to the famous scene of Roman soldiers playing dice for the garments of Jesus Christ after his crucifixion, I was curious how I could have overlooked such an iconic scene, only to find that they were not playing dice but “casting lots”, the most basic generation of chance. While it is mentioned in abundance within the Hebrew Tanakh, this scene remains almost unique in the New Testament, so I was happy to even find it described in the *Oxford History of Board Games* (Parlett, 2018, p.21):

“Whether or not they (The Romans throwing the lot for Jesus garments) were technically ‘playing a game’ is arguable. Certainly, the association between gambling and playing is strong enough for religious leaders through the ages to condemn play by tarring it with the same brush as that used for casting lots.”

It was under this broad brush that I wanted to take a detailed look. Roger Caillois sharply pointed out that playing with chance is only observed among humans (Caillois, 1958), while animals also compete, mimic, or seek useless rushes of adrenaline, according to his four categories of play. Surely the belief in higher powers or divine forces is one of the things that we think makes us human, but apparently chance is another, so I wanted to know exactly how the opposing ideas of randomness and determined fate had been linked together. With existing research on the effects of chance on animals, I wanted to know when and why did “Homo Aleatorius” emerge? From estimating risk and return to the rise of AI, the control over chance has come to dominate our lives, so perhaps the cultivation of chance was the one missing link from animal to artificial intelligence. I therefore ask:

How was chance cultivated?

PRIMARY PROBLEM – STATUS OF RESEARCH

Only a limited number of studies exist about the practice of casting lots in general, but most academic work stems from the field of religious studies due to the frequent mentions of casting lots in the Bible, therefore suggesting a principal bias towards the divine origin of the concept of chance. While abundant research exists concerning gambling as well as in religious context, this thesis aims to focus on the pure production of chance as in intentional randomness as a cultural technique (Siegert, 2020) in contrast to betting stakes.

This thesis questions the prevalent academic view that games of chance have emerged out of divination by lots which is reproduced in many works that can be associated with game studies. In *Roll the bones – a history of gambling* (Schwartz, 2006, p.3) it is written that “Cleromancy, the casting of lots, would gradually evolve from sacred ritual to profane amusement – dice.” and David Parlett states that: “Lots in gaming have been held to derive from a primary use in divination and soothsaying, with a secondary stage in which they are used as a way of making decisions impartially.” (Parlett, 2018, p.21). Upon looking up the sources, both have quoted from E. B. Tylor and his foundational book *Primitive culture* (Tylor, 1871) that would open the field of anthropology. It was most likely taken as a secondary quote via *The study of games* (Avedon & Sutton-Smith, 1971, p. 70) where it is also found. But in his vast work E. B. Tylor only very briefly touched upon the practice of casting lots and describing the difference between using lots for gaming and divination as being the difference between “will” and “shall” (1871, chapter 3). A very loose interpretation to rest a claim of this size on, especially since the modern corpus of research must have evolved.

Florence Nightingale David first researched the history of probability and statistical ideas in her book *Games, Gods and Gambling* and described what came first – recreational chance or divination by chance – as a chicken-or-egg problem (David, 1962, p.13). Ian Hacking also concerns himself, why some anthropologists see sortilege or divination as the origin of many simple games of chance, pointing out the utter lack of research concerning chance and asks: “We should not ask, why did people fail to study these objects? We should ask instead, how did these objects of thought come into being?” (Hacking, 1975, p.9). Concerning the concept of chance as “objects of thought” accurately describes what I seek to study. Simultaneously studying the objects that might create them appears to be a good approach.

I drew further inspiration from archeologist Peter Piccione and his analysis of the earliest board games uncovered from about 3000 BCE in Egypt as funerary offerings to bring along to the afterlife. Tutankhamen for example had games complete with binary lots in the form of casting sticks. As more game boards were found, a pattern appeared: The earliest ones would be blank but as time progressed some fields would be decorated with Hieroglyphs, symbols which had also just been in development. The earliest wall paintings of Egyptian board gamers would be two people playing and boasting about their wins, while later ones also featured a single person only, like Queen Nefertari being shown with the game alone¹. By that time, we know the game to be called “Senet”, meaning “passing”, and it was also featured in the *Book of the Dead* (Budge, 1895) dated around 1250 BCE where Ani and his wife play the game with their bird-like spirits above the sarcophagus. Piccione proposed that by that time the Egyptians had “superimposed their beliefs onto the gameboard” and that “Senet was originally strictly a pastime with no religious significance.” (Piccione, 1980)

From my previous study of architecture I remember my amazement that all the great theatres and stadiums of European antiquity that I have so associated with its culture – for spectacles of tragic-comic plays, brutal gladiator fights, intense races or the glory of the Olympic games – were all put to rest for a millennia as pagan practices of idolatry through the power of writings like *De Spectaculis* (Tertullian, c. 200 CE). Bread & games had been replaced with bread & wine of the church and even though we have played since the dawn of time, we simply did not have a perspective of game studies since the most recent human stage because play certainly did not have a high status within the Christian realm of thought.

Whether it is anthropology, archeology or religious studies it is within the dusty boxes labeled “divination” or “magic” one must look for answers in game studies.

¹ See **figure 5 & 6** on page 55.

METHODOLOGY

To answer the question "How was chance cultivated?" this thesis will investigate both the objects used as lots as well as the objects of thought they have created. This will be done within an established frame of reference to be able to locate them on a spectrum of use cases. Therefore, the thesis will be constructed of three major parts:

- A. Framework of reference
- B. Lots as physical objects
- C. Lots as objects of thought

It must first and foremost be clarified what "a lot" is, and what the perspective of game studies is. It further needs to be established what a common understanding of chance and divination is, since this appears to be the commonly held origin of games of chance within the current academic corpus. Using the most academically accepted literature, an initial frame of reference therefore seeks to clarify fundamental definitions, characteristics, and intentions of a lot: Play, chance, and divination. The answers will then be juxtaposed onto another to create a framework of reference described in part A:

A. Framework of reference between Play, Divination and Decision making

Diagram 1

B. Lots as objects and their performative qualities

Objects used for lots will then be categorized. First by logic of established literature like *The Oxford history of board games*, (Parlett, 2018) into binary lots like coins, poly lots like dice or unique lots as used in sortition, as well as by their archeological appearance or natural availability like Astragals, the Talus bones of sheep used as dice. Lastly the use of these lots will be treated as cultural techniques (Siegert, 2020) and analyzed according to their performative qualities like “flipping” a coin, “drawing” a stick, “casting” dice or “spinning” a coconut. The most noteworthy characteristics are then analyzed according to the established framework of part A whether they are suitable for play, divination, or potential other purposes. The use of lots as a cultural technique will make up part B.

C. Lots as objects of thought in their historic context

With this nuanced perspective and intellectual toolset of fine brushes, the practice of casting lots will then be located on the full spectrum of its usability within the earliest records and foundational literature in shaping human thought. The earliest Mesopotamian myths, Sanskrit mythology, the Abrahamic holy books, as well as Greek and Roman mythology and philosophy. They all described some use of lots and were fundamental in shaping literal objects of thought concerning chance in a cultural context long before it was formalized in mathematical terms. It will be analyzed if Gods or deities were in control of chance or not, in what context lots were cast, if there were any initial intentions declared and what the outcome of the process ultimately was. It will also be documented how the word “lot” was mostly used in its original languages and if and how its meaning had changed over time. The play element of culture (Huizinga, 1955) concerning chance and randomness will therefore be mapped out in part C.

Each part will be ended with a compressed summary to give the reader an easy insight into the most significant findings, or to choose which specific aspect to expand into. Game studies terminology will be written in SMALL CAPS and a glossary will be provided (p. 110).

The goal is to conclude with a coherent overview on the use and evolution of lots along with the cultivation of chance as a cultural technique.

LOT

A “lot” is a random decision maker, like a coin-flip, drawing the short end of a stick, or a lot from a “lottery”. Anything from sticks, stones, bones, shells, pieces of paper, broken clay or specifically crafted pieces can be used as lots. Dice are specifically crafted lots mostly used in games and therefore represent a subcategory of lots. So, while every form of casting dice is a form of casting lots, it is not the case the other way around and cannot be used interchangeably.

LOT - ETYMOLOGY

The word lot comes from Old English as well as Old High German “hlot”, meaning “an object used for deciding something by chance” but is also referred to as “a share” or a “portion” like the old Norse word “hlutr”.² The Proto-Germanic root “hlutan” similarly means “to cast lots, draw lots, or divide by lot” as in to “allot”. In Old High German it was also referred to as “fate”. By the 15th century, the Germanic concept of a lot was absorbed into Italian as the word “Lotto” which has been made popular by the early 1620s as what we now understand as a “lottery”, which is quite the same as sortition. The Latin word for lot is “sors” (plural: sortes) from which the word for “sortition” derives. Among those languages its use a verb is only found in German with “losen”, while others mostly necessitate an action as in “casting” or “drawing” the object(s), lots.

The Greek word for lot is “κλήρος” which also represents the etymological root of “cleric” as in a class of priests, while “cleromancy” is a divination method using lots. The ancient Greeks of the early Attic democracy used lots to assign democratic mandates and before that used lots to assign conquered land among its citizens called the Cleruchy. The term of “a lot of land” - as in a plot - derived from the practice of land division by lot or “allotment” which is documented in the Tanakh and throughout the ancient Near East from the earliest times of Mesopotamia as part of its inheritance law. The Hebrew word גֹרָל (Goral) often found in the Tanakh has its root ג-ר-ל associated with actions like “casting”, “rolling” or generally “moving” small objects like a pebble (Klein, 1987), but likewise meant “portion” as well as “fate” or “destiny”, as in one’s “lot in life”. This remains the modern usage of the word.

² <https://www.etymonline.com/>

A. FRAMEWORK OF REFERENCE

1. GAME STUDIES

HOMO LUDENS

The essence and controversy of *Homo Ludens – A study of the play element in culture* (Huizinga, 1955, origin. 1938) can already be found in the title, to which the author, Dutch anthropologist and cultural historian Johan Huizinga never agreed to and therefore protests in his foreword that his publisher repeatedly corrected his original subtitle “A study of the play element OF culture” to IN culture. But Huizinga did not attempt to analyze play or games in different cultures, but to portray culture itself as a form of play, which is why the chapters of *Homo Ludens* have names like “Play and Contest as civilizing functions”, “Play and War”, “Play and Law”, “Play and Poetry”, “Play-forms in Philosophy”, etc. He also located religion, magic, liturgy, and mystery within the play-sphere. Huizinga theorized that all culture emerged from play, eventually evolving into ritual, and ultimately becoming institutionalized or common practice. But the initial play-world was described by him as a voluntary activity with an aim in itself (like joy), separated from the real world bound by its own rules within a designated time and space.

THE SACRED EARNEST

The “Magic Circle” had become the primary concept of game studies to describe this play-sphere. But Huizinga himself had only mentioned this term once in his book and even then, only among counting certain colorful descriptions of a playground. But the term has stuck and represents one of the beautiful serendipities in cultural science. The term he would use is “SACRED EARNEST”, as a mutual understanding to uphold the play-sphere and its order.

“Play is not “ordinary” or “real” but the contrast between play and seriousness is always fluid (...) inside the playground an absolute and peculiar order reigns (...) As soon as the rules are transgressed the whole play-world collapses. The game is over.” (p.8, 10)

When kids play catch, they know who “it” is, as well as the rule of who becomes “it”. It is negotiated and agreed upon without much talking but is upheld by all participants with SACRED EARNEST to create this magical play-world where they are all running around highly energized having a tremendous amount of fun. This is the aim in itself and they have all volunteered to be in it. But “it” doesn’t count anymore once the game is over. This same “magic” is observed among animals like when dogs play catch and “bite” each other without actually biting. They merely pretend and know that they are in the play world.

THE PLAY ELEMENT OF CULTURE

Huizinga roughly located two aspects of play as either “a contest *for* something or a representation *of* something” (Huizinga, 1955, p.13). In this sense Huizinga explores a wide range of societal phenomena that might not be identified as play but on the contrary can be very much linked to serious activities with a lot at stake, possibly resulting in loss of economic well-being or even death. For example:

- Gift-exchange (Potlatch): Outdoing one another in generosity. (chapt. III)
- Legal trials: Combative, verbal battles to determine justice. (chapt. IV)
- War: Honorable contests between equals according to rules. (chapt. V)
- Business: A contest of fortune or to make the best product. (chapt. VIII)
- Public debates: Competitive displays of learning and wit. (chapt. IX)

Concerning the most blatant example, war: If the sole purpose would be to simply kill a threat or to satisfy one’s need for safety, food, health, or comfort no one would participate in useless formalities, exemplified by European style warfare of the 18th and 19th century with large armies of distinctly colored uniforms meeting on a battle ground at a specific agreed upon time to engage in a highly orchestrated mass murder. Also, in civil societies of today one volunteers for an army where combatants are marked to distinguish them from non-combatants. And in his example of ritualized Native American gift-giving competitions, the Potlatch, “the opposed groups do not contend for wealth or power but simply for the pleasure of parading their superiority” (p. 59) It is comparable to who gets to pay the dinner-check which serves no material gain but rather stems from cultural rules of honor.

“Though play as such is outside the range of good and bad, the element of tension imparts to it a certain ethical value in so far as it means a testing of the player’s prowess: his courage, tenacity, resources and, last but not least, his spiritual powers – his “fairness”; because, despite his ardent desire to win, he must still stick to the rules of the game.” (p. 11)

The play element of culture therefore represents the civilizing part. Huizinga famously brought the example of the spoilsport as being less tolerated than a cheat, who secretly bypasses rules to gain an unfair advantage, and if exposed be expelled from the play-sphere. A spoilsport to the contrary would break the whole play-sphere of SACRED EARNEST for everyone and cannot be tolerated at all. (p.11)

PLAY AND GAMES

With the book *Man, Play and Games* (1958) Roger Caillois provided a major contribution to game studies where he expands on Huizinga and also examines the means by which games become part of daily life and ultimately contribute to various cultural customs and institutions, but puts less focus on Huizinga’s observation about the play element of culture but instead attempted to classify and categorize different types of play in a structured framework. He also critiques that “games of chance played for money have practically no place in Huizinga’s work” (Caillois, 1958, p.5)

Similarly, to Huizinga he defines play as being “free, separate, uncertain, and unproductive, governed by rules and make-believe” (Caillois, 1958, p. 9-10) The noteworthy addition being that all play has an inherent uncertainty, from which the excitement or fun emerges.

He explains the dichotomy between ways of playing, ranging from the free and unrestricted improvisational characteristic of children's play he termed “PAIDIA” and the arbitrary and disciplined “LUDUS”. (p. 13) In game studies this would become the differentiation of Play vs. Games. (Salen & Zimmerman, 2004)

Apart from this range of unrestricted and formalized play and contrary to the two aspects of Huizinga, competition, and simulation, Caillois classified four types of play (p. 12):

Table 1

AGÔN (competition)	ALEA (chance)
MIMICRY (pretending)	ILINX (thrill-seeking)

His two additions also feature the same characteristic in having to intentionally give up AGENCY, while the former two demand some form of skill.

AGENCY and skill	Giving up AGENCY
------------------	------------------

AGÔN (competition)

Competition in any sense whether it is a physical sporting competition like tennis, soccer or boxing or a competition of wit like a game of chess and even solving riddles, as one competes against a created play-world to test one's intelligence. Caillois mentions the need for an artificially leveled playing field for competition in a playful sense to provide fairness and equal opportunity to decide who is best. (Ibid. p.14)

ALEA (chance)

“ALEA” is derived from the Latin word for dice (p. 17) as in the famous saying “alea iacta est” attributed to Julius Caesar, which translates to “the dice are cast”. With the decision to play with ALEA the thrill derives from the pure uncertainty of the outcome with one’s own AGENCY or skill having no influence in contrast to AGÔN. The only AGENCY available is the choice to cast or not to cast.

MIMICRY (role-playing, or make pretend)

Playing as in pretending or acting as someone or something else. Whether it is the childish free play of pretending to be an animal or playing with dolls or the structured form of a theater play. MIMICRY is also the essential part of observing a spectacle like attending a sporting event, where one is not actively the player, but still takes part in the game like dressing in team colors to pretend and culturally bond. (p. 23)

ILINX (disorientating oneself, thrill-seeking and risk taking)

The joy of being intoxicated or disoriented. (p. 23) Often the most difficult to describe as a category, but in many ways the very essence of play due to its inherent uselessness, but inherent joy. As if tricking our internal chemical reward system to gain pleasure it represents the rush of Adrenalin when jumping off a cliff, whirling oneself into ecstasy or a dog chasing its own tail. Doing unreasonable or dangerous things is just pure fun.

Caillois highlights the essence of the 4 categories by comparing them in 6 combinations:

Fundamental relationships (p.74-79)

He points out that AGÔN and ALEA complement each other perfectly and frequently, like in card, dice or board games as a competition of players with each having more or less AGENCY of making their own decisions and moves, but also being subject to the roll of dice or the shuffled deck and having to evaluate the risk. Since both AGÔN and ALEA require structure and a minimal set of rules, they are more located in the sphere of LUDUS, while MIMICRY and ILINX on the other hand are easier to be located within the sphere of PAIDIA, since they are more unrestricted in its playfulness. (p. 75)

Contingent and forbidden relationships (p.72,73)

Both AGÔN and MIMICRY are contingent. Both require skill and are easily turned into a spectacle of theater or sports. Caillois points out that cultural spheres who value those activities also put more emphasis on merit (p. 78). AGÔN and ILINX on the other hand negate each other in requiring or defying structure.

ALEA and ILINX both need no skill at all but share their attempt to let go of as much AGENCY as possible. (p.73) Getting intoxicated or whirling oneself into ecstasy takes no skill and there is no way to train for a pure game of chance other than cheating. But both ALEA and ILINX also form a contingent relationship closely brought in context with the divine. Like the Pythia of the oracle Delphi is unbiased due to its intoxication and open to be receiving the divine outside of themselves and rid of one's own AGENCY.

“Games of chance have been associated with divination in the same way games of strength or skill or riddle contests had probative value in the enthronement rituals for an important responsibility or ministry.” (p.60)

He points out that „Games of chance would seem to be peculiarly human. Animals play games involving competition, stimulation, and excess.“ (p. 18), but in his appendix “On the importance of games of chance” dismisses ALEA as having any institutional value only to be used in rare cases like the Athenian democracy (p.158). However, this thesis argues the contrary, that casting lots existed as a cultural technique for eons and would be a foundational institution in most pre-literary societies. This is described in detail within the historical section of this thesis starting on page 73.

MEANINGFUL PLAY

Rules of Play (2004) by Salen & Zimmerman is a comprehensive attempt to capture the world of play in a structured framework. Beyond the imagination of Huizinga and Caillois, it belongs to a new era of looking at play after the emergence of video games, with new types of games, cultural phenomena, and the job title “game designer”. Its subtitle “Game Design Fundamentals” shows the different intention, not as an anthropological observation or philosophical deconstruction, but as a primal toolkit for a craft.

Salen & Zimmerman assert that play can manifest in three ways:

1. when being playful (like dressing or talking playfully, or inventing slang words)
2. in playful activities (such as playing in a sandbox or with a ball)
3. in game play (a structured and therefore designed form)

“MEANINGFUL PLAY” according to Salen and Zimmerman, is the primary goal of game design, which they refer to as a “tight coupling” between a player’s action with the designed system that is a game and the game’s response or outcome (p.137) to create engaging experiences. Karl Kapp would emphasize that games evoke strong emotions due to the “instant, direct, and clear” feedback games provide (Kapp, 2012, p. 8) as fundamental to games similar to the experience of Flow (Csíkszentmihályi, 1970).

In play, like being immersed within a sandbox, there is no winning state, so similar to Caillois, Salen & Zimmerman separate Play (PAIDIA) from Games (LUDUS) considering games as a formalized “subset of play” and add to the notion of rules that a game is inherently agonistic with “measurable feedback”, like scoring a point, when writing:

“A game is a system in which players engage in an artificial conflict, defined by rules, that results in a quantifiable outcome” (p. 80).

It is exactly this measurable feedback and quantifiable outcome that will form an integral part of this thesis in analyzing lots, its use, and its meaning.

ILLUSTRATING GAME STUDIES TERMINOLGY

To illustrate the basic concepts and terminology presented on the previous pages, I would like to conclude with a thought experiment on how we could imagine the design of casting lots from a perspective of game studies. The basic terms are also summed up in the glossary on page 110.

The act of casting represents a technique of primal human AGENCY by using our hands. Learning to cast stones can provide various real-life benefits in hunting and defending oneself against aggressors. In this case there is no play-aspect involved since it serves our function of survival and is no aim in itself. However, we observe a child collecting a bunch of sticks, leaves, stones, sand, or anything it can get ahold of and joyfully throwing it in the air. This represents a playful act in purity of PAIDIA. It serves no purpose other than to be joyful, since “Throwing things is fun.”

When we then engage in applying certain rules, we will transform this playful action of PAIDIA into LUDUS. A hyperbolic primitive game could be to see who can throw a rock the farthest or throwing rocks at a tree and determining who hits it first or more often. It could stem from training for the real-life ability of hunting and defending, which could result in higher social status and honor, but we merely pretend “as if” and have nothing to gain from it or to defend from. The player’s AGENCY is using one’s strength and precision to develop different techniques to win in this competitive game of skill. It is therefore AGÔN as well as fitting the definition of Salen & Zimmerman, since we can measure a quantifiable outcome of who has thrown farthest or heard who hit the tree, maybe even seeing a mark on it to serve as proof. It will be our result who wins and gains honor.

How would we go about turning this into a game of ALEA? If we would sit on the edge of a cliff and merely drop rocks without aim, we would be back at PAIDIA. If we want to create some quantifiable result we’d have to agree where or how the rock lands to win, but to keep it within ALEA, we will then have to make sure that we get rid of any intention to aim or throw in a certain way. We could close our eyes and throw it behind our backs or turn around our axis into the dizziness of ILINX and then let go to add even more randomness. We would want to create a situation where one can’t aim but still manages to throw and create a result.

A different way would be if we could find or create an object that has distinguishable sides and manage to agree on a certain outcome, which we understand as dice, and that the object has to be cast in such a way to ensure a maximum number of turns and the person doing so will be closely monitored to do just that, without cheating. This would already need an application of meaning to each of those sides, instead of a mere quantifiable outcome of hit or no-hit and it would need significantly more rules.

And a third example to create ALEA would be to skip the act of casting and hide a little pebble between one of our two hands and let someone else pick blindly. To turn this into a game is easy: Whoever guesses better, wins. But one side would need some skill to hide as well as possible while the other side could try to use some skill to guess by looking at one's grip or deep into one's eyes to get a reaction. To generate ALEA the guessing person would have to show to be willing to give up all AGENCY and pick blindly.

All these examples could create a game with a quantifiable outcome, defined by rules engaging in an artificial conflict, with the outcome determined by chance instead of skill. But we would have to demand absolute fairness that each player willingly gives up as much AGENCY as possible and to trust one another on that. The pressure on keeping up the rules - as simple as they may be - and honoring our bond with SACRED EARNEST is much higher with ALEA and represents a very structured form of LUDUS.

If this trust is high enough, we could use it to create a random decision whenever we want without needing a game to win something. And if we continue to use this practice in our daily lives in dealing with each other we will have a play element of culture emerging.

GAMBLING VS. GAMES OF CHANCE

Playing with chance is often associated with gambling. However, the main feature of gambling is betting or staking. One needs to risk something one can lose so that one can win someone else's bet, otherwise it isn't gambling. Every game has an inherently uncertain outcome, whether it is subject to chance or competition. When one bets on a horse race or a boxing match, the outcome is decided by the skill of the contestants (AGÔN), not by chance (ALEA), even when the gambler placing bets on the sidelines has no AGENCY over the outcome. Gambling with pure chance, like dice or at a slot-machine, is therefore a subset of gambling using chance (ALEA). One can gamble whether one wins at a game of chess, with all the AGENCY among the players. The essence of gambling among people is staking, which has a cultural link to Huizinga's descriptions of Potlatch's as resembling the atmosphere of "gambling dens". But like arguing who gets to pay the dinner check it is competitive gift giving, as he writes, to show one's status (emphasis by author, Huizinga, 1955, p. 58).

To carve out the details let's consider a game of Poker: Even though the underlying game is indeed based on the randomness what cards are being dealt and about the chances of favorable combinations. The essence of the game is the AGÔN of boasting and staking while on the other hand folding one's cards and retreating from a bet one is not sure about, instead of being dragged into losing more than one can handle. Good bluffing (MIMICRY) is the main skill in Poker, and it mixes well with AGÔN (as the contingent relationship shown on page 14). It is also a good skill for any player of Poker to be well versed in the understanding of probability to evaluate the risk of certain possible combinations. But even if one happens to hold the best hand possible (like a straight flush with a high Aces) which will win the pot with absolute certainty, the necessary skill will still be the MIMICRY of good bluffing to make one's opponents believe that they actually have a chance so that they pool more of their money into the pot, which one will win with certainty in the end.

Games of Poker can be ruthless AGÔN, where an equality of opportunity is not even essential. In a cash game where each player can buy in with as much chips as one can afford, the rich player will always be in favor. If one player starts with 200 compared to others starting with only 10, it is a game of almost pure power and the likelihood that the rich player quickly eats up the weaker ones is almost certain. But this is not due to the underlying randomness of the card dealing, or the skill of MIMICRY, but due to the probability of strength.

A. FRAMEWORK OF REFERENCE

2. UNCERTAINTY

ANIMALS AND CHANCE

Uncertainty is part of life, and uncertainty is also the main characteristic of any game (Elias, Garfield, & Gutschera, 2012, p. 137) no matter if it is decided by skill or chance, since it would be boring to know exactly what will happen and how the outcome will be. But a fundamental question for this thesis is why we are the only species to actively engage in artificial uncertainty by playing with chance like Roger Caillois had pointed out.

AGÔN as in competition is of course the easiest to recognize when animals show or challenge a status among hierarchies. Not just in brutal earnest, but in playful ways and accepting when one gives up. Animals do cooperate to compete. Concerning MIMICRY there are various ways like dances and rituals to show off one's mating partner as well as to mimic to manipulate and deceive in competitions, which doesn't mean cheating but for example feinting an attack. To play something "as if" is likewise a great skill and serves as a significant cultural bond within the societies of animals as well. ILINX is observed frequently among animals in the likes of submitting oneself to the thrill of Adrenalin of being in free fall, subject to forces of the waves or being tossed into dizziness. While AGÔN and MIMICRY can always be interpreted as offering real life value due to its basis on skill like simulating or training for something, none of the playful observations we can attribute to ILINX serve any function or training for survival or finding mating partners. One can go as far as saying the essence of ILINX is doing nonsensical, stupid, or plainly dangerous things that offer absolutely nothing to gain. But apparently, we can agree within the large family of mammals, that doing nonsensical things is incredibly pleasing and fun (Toomy, 2024).

But when animals engage in playful risk-taking activities by swinging from high branches for example, we must reject this as playing with chance (ALEA) as uncertainty is an elemental aspect of every kind of play. We are an entirely different species in actively seeking and cultivating ALEA, even though when it comes to its effects on our brains we are not so different than any other animal.

THE NEUROSCIENCE OF RANDOMNESS

The effects of chance, randomness and the evaluation of risk and return in animals has been studied and documented. In *Schedules of Reinforcement*, (1957) Skinner and Ferster explored how different reinforcement schedules affected pigeon's behavior and endurance. They set up experiments so that the pigeons actively engaged with an apparatus to receive rewards that either had fixed, variable, or random schedules. The pigeons were trained to peck a button to obtain a desired outcome, food. Their behavior was measured and quantified through the AGENCY they exhibited through pecking the button, which demonstrated their active role in the reinforcement process with different rates of response. The study found three basic types of incentives:

Fixed Interval

One tap or pecking results in one food pellet, every time. Animals figure this out quickly and don't get excited about it. They realize that this is the certain way to get food which will quickly become boring.

Changing Interval

For example, if the fixed pattern is changed every other day to two taps, and on the next day perhaps to a long tap, and the day after to a long tap and two short taps, etc. this provides a stimulative puzzle that gets the animals excited and engaged to figure out how to get food on each new day. It understands the rules of the game and engages in MEANINGFUL PLAY.

Variable Interval

In these scenarios, tapping the button or lever provided an average amount of food every hour, its distribution however was entirely randomized, which could result in abundance in one hour and virtually nothing the next. The results were now not only stimulative but entirely addictive and the everlasting suspense would cause the pigeons to frantically peck the button. To highlight the level of engagement resulting from variable intervals, consider the following observation:

"By the end of the study, pigeons were pecking a food lever up to five times per second for as long as fifteen hours without pausing longer than fifteen or twenty seconds during the whole period." (emphasis added by author, p.155)

Within our categories of play, the first “fixed” example is quickly outside of the play-range since it is certain and therefore boring. But the difference between the “changing” and “variable” examples also represent the difference between AGÔN and ALEA, since the “changing” example is based on the uncertainty based on the skill of the pigeon to solve the riddle, while the “variable” example is based on the complete randomness of ALEA. The pigeon however is simply not aware that it has no AGENCY, but still “believes” it has.

Superstitions in pigeons (1948) was the original studies that B.F. Skinner based their book on, since it described the emergent behavior to figure out a way to get food. For example, pigeons would hop from side to side in a certain way or twist one’s head before engaging with pecking the lever, because the pigeons have already started to think outside the box and to consider that their behavior apart from the interaction with the system might be relevant to the outcome, which it wasn’t. In slot machines a “feeling of AGENCY” is highlighted by giant levers which communicate a sense of power and control, while in fact it is the absolute opposite, by letting go of any AGENCY. The only AGENCY that remains within games of pure chance is to either stop or continue, while stopping means returning to the boring certainty of gaining no reward. The broad relationship between superstition and ALEA can therefore be supported by seeking non-existent patterns within randomness, with general behavioral observation and biochemical results.

Dopamine is the primal learning and self-conditioning mechanism of reward-motivated behavior, that is tricked by engaging with artificial randomness. Slot-machines and most social media feeds use it to frequently reward the user with something pleasing without ever knowing when, to keep engagement up. Dopamine engages within the brain upon received rewards and tells it to repeat the same action to obtain it again. Looking for patterns programs the brain on new ways to obtain food or to be cautious for survival when a bush moves. The human brain is no different as *Brains seek patterns in coincidences* (Beitman, 2009).

People tend to see nonexistent patterns in random sequences, as well as believing in “hot streaks” when rolling several good throws of dice in a row. The psychologists Kahneman and Tversky (1977, 1979, 1982) have intensively studied how ordinary people face an inherent difficulty in understanding randomness and how statistical principles are not learned from everyday experience. Explaining a lot of irrational human economic choices, they find that people typically do not attend to necessary detail to gain such knowledge (p. 8–9, 24).

A different aspect from the effects of randomness is the evaluation of risk. A study with macaque monkeys provided different rewards with different levels of risk (McCoy & Platt, 2005) and provided many insights into the perception of risk and return with our closer relatives from the animal kingdom. Macaques are quite rational risk-takers and are more reward-driven when making economic decisions than humans. They are also less biased by framing effects (Chen, 2006), meaning if a gamble is framed as a potential gain versus a potential loss. Kahneman and Tversky (1979) demonstrated that humans dislike losing much more than we enjoy winning. But macaques make risky decisions based on immediate reward probabilities, while humans engage in more strategic and long-term risk assessment and risk aversion. Perhaps this more cautious behavior and ability to plan ahead played a role in humans eventually taking chance into their own hands by casting lots. An ability that would be well within the capability of our close ape ancestors and their agile hands, as well as the potential for symbol recognition and even basic arithmetic (Cantlon & Brannon, 2006). They can be trained in video games to navigate mazes or match objects for rewards, but struggle with task-switching and strategy (Procyk et al., 2000), which would however not even be necessary for the simplicity of casting lots. The limited rule flexibility compared to humans makes me point out our obvious difference to our animal relatives: The use of language. I therefore suggest that casting lots has more of a cultural origin than being an intellectual breakthrough.

However, a last example from the animal world may be hinting in a different direction: *Play in Common Ravens (Corvus corax)* (1991) by ethnologists Bernd Heinrich and Rachel Smolker observed a raven in solitude picking up a stone at the edge of a cliff and tossing it off the edge to watch it fall and then to find it again and repeat the process. Nothing about it could be about community status, mating partners or practicing any sort of skill necessary for their survival in obtaining food, and they concluded in amazement that the raven did it merely for fun. We could be very picky and argue that it could be a bit of AGÔN if the intention is to test one's skill to find the rock again, or that it could be a bit of ILINX in just trying to do nonsensical things. But it is not AGÔN with the intention of hitting something specific nor ILINX in the sense that it is to intoxicate oneself in a rush of Adrenalin. It is fun to simply drop something, to let go, and then to observe what happens. Could this be the most primal form of ALEA? Staying confined to my field of cultural studies, I cannot make any valuable assumptions here, but hope for more research on chance and animals in the future.

UNCERTAINTY AND ITS VARIATIONS OF THOUGHT

As already established, uncertainty is both an essential part of life as well as the main characteristic of any game (Elias, Garfield, & Gutschera, 2012, p. 137). Especially the correlation between uncertainty, certainty and chance can be described concerning the example of a six-sided die. One can be absolutely certain that it is impossible to roll a 7 with a six-sided die, and it is certain that one will have the chance of 1/6 to roll any of the numbers, even though it remains completely uncertain, unpredictable and random, which of the 6 numbers it eventually will be. Mathematician Richard Epstein wrote about chance as risk in *The Theory of gambling and statistical Logic* (2009, p. 175):

“In a game of risk, you can be completely certain about the degree of uncertainty in the outcome.”

This means that we will always have some sort of controlled system of uncertainty within a game of chance or risk. But I would think there is a semantic difference between risk and chance, with the first implying a stake that can be lost and the latter always having a quantifiable outcome. Capital markets for example seek to calculate the chances of risk and return based on a variety of factors like average demand, median income, savings, interest rates, etc. as if multiple different numbers of dice with different sides and multiple throws are used. It is seeking to quantify risk on a map of uncertainty to certainty and calculate the odds. Odds that may rapidly change with disruptions like wars, and capital markets typically have difficulties with completely random events like a pandemic causing much uncertainty. Risk anticipates a good or bad outcome, while chance seeks to quantify it.

Randomness refers to a lack of predictability or pattern in events or outcomes. Concerning the roll of dice, it does not matter if a 6 has been rolled 10 times in a row, the next outcome would still be as unpredictable and with the equal chance as any other before.

In the context of game design input randomness and output randomness are terms often used with systems involving chance. Input randomness emphasizes reactive strategy, like players having to roll dice at the beginning of a turn and then having to adapt to the random outcomes like landing on a certain field providing one with different options. Output randomness is used after a decision has been made, like going to war in a game of *Risk* (Hasbro, 1957) with 5 against 3 armies, and then letting dice determine whether the attack succeeds or fails.

Let us imagine a random event that occurs by complete accident. For example, a die that does not produce a definite outcome because it got stuck on the edge of the carpet by some way. When playing games that include chance, we therefore aim to exclude as much external randomness to the system as much as possible to have equal chances for all. For example, by having a flat surface with boundaries for rolling dice.

But while all of the previous examples provide intentionally clear and definite outcomes within the system of the dice and rules, I would like to contrast that with the complete uncertainty of randomness as in chaos. Randomness can still revolve around an order like dice, spinning a teetotum or a wheel of Fortune revolving around its own axis. But chaos has no order. As an example, I would like to bring forth a tradition of divination we like to do in Austria for New Year's Day, which consists of melting a piece of lead and then pouring it into cold water which will instantly cool off and harden into a completely random shape. It can then only be interpreted by seeing a non-existent pattern and association if it looks like a fish, a tree or whatever comes to one's mind which can then be further interpreted what it may possibly mean for the year to come. This is divination, but there is absolutely no certainty about the degree of uncertainty here. The outcome is entirely random, but not quantifiable.

Luck on the other hand is usually attached with a strong emotion when something good or bad happens to one, whether it be with or without anticipation, by coincidence, when in dire need or just out of the blue. Missing a flight that later crashes is extremely lucky as one anticipated the opposite. Luck does not need uncertainty, risk, chance or chaotic randomness, but can definitely be augmented by it. It is an entirely personal experience.

One can produce something intentionally uncertain by playing, something chaotic by splattering paint on a wall, something random by spinning a wheel or something risky by betting stakes. However, the original meaning of chance would be "by accident", meaning something happening completely unintentionally and unanticipated. But today it is much closer associated with probability and a quantifiable outcome.

There is no clear academic set of definitions, and common language has continuously evolved its meaning, while the human mind generally associates these differing concepts with one another. The evolution of these "objects of thought" will be covered in the historical section of this thesis starting on page 73.

PROBABILTY

The word “probable” stems from Latin, “probabilism”, meaning “provable”, “credible”, or “likely”. First probabilists were Italians of the 16th century, like mathematician Blaise Pascal, solving North African problems in “Hazard” (David, 1962, p.6). F.N. David states that the old word for risk or chance “Hazard” is as Arabic as “Algebra”, deriving from the word for dice “al zahr” (p. 34). With *Liber de ludo aleae* [The Book on Games of Chance] (1663) by Giacomo Cardano, probability got formalized in mathematical models like 50:50 or fractions like 5/8.

Even though the actual study of probability only emerged in Renaissance Italy of the 16th century, Ian Hacking (1975) points out that this is merely our concept of probability in formalized mathematics, and points to the missing mathematical field of arithmetic for much of human history. Simple counting, either by hand or using piles of stones, has been part of human cultural techniques for much longer than recorded history along with using marked lines or dots. The abacus, developed in Mesopotamia around 2500 BC has helped to represent large numbers but was limited to addition or subtraction. The Hindu concept of zero was adapted by the Arabs and its Hindu-Arabic numerical system of 10 integers only later spread into the Christians realm, replacing the long-standing abacus and Roman numerical system. This numerical system together with the concept of fractions would be our basic understanding of probability today, to be able to calculate chance and risk.

Hacking pointed to the ancient Hindu epic of the Mahabharata as an example of a knowledge of probability³. A key story-point is the gambling away of the kingdom in a game of dice between the legal heirs and their cousins. During their years in exile the family hears the story of Nala, learning the art of dice from a snake king in a forest after he predicted the exact amount of fruit and leaves on a tree⁴. Hacking suggests this is to be a description of an ancient wisdom of probability (Hacking, 1975, p.7), when the snake king proclaimed:

*“I of dice possess the science.
And in numbers thus am skilled.”* (Milman, 1890, p.76)

³ The story and its mentions of dice is analyzed on page 101-102 in the historical section of this thesis.

⁴ A tree of knowledge symbolism.

SUMMARY UNCERTAINTY

Uncertainty is a fundamental part of life with the future being largely unpredictable. Animals and humans alike seek to make sense of uncertainty by locating patterns within randomness to secure more certain paths for survival, which is rewarded with dopamine.

But humans are unique in creating games with artificial and intentional randomness.

Uncertainty is also a fundamental characteristic of all games, where it is intentional and by design, whether determined by skill or chance. Gambling however is not fundamentally about randomness or chance but about staking something of value on an uncertain outcome with the risk of losing it, not be mistaken with purely chance-based play like rolling dice.

Early societies lacked a mathematical framework to describe probability due to being largely confined to numerals but a lack of arithmetic. This however does not provide any evidence for their lack of conceptualizing chance and having to solely resort to superstition. Likewise, many different concepts concerning uncertainty have been mixed up in common language and understanding and have only gradually evolved into a process of differentiation. A process that is ongoing and always subject to change. For this thesis the ideas will be used as follows and can also be retrieved from the glossary on page 110:

Chance: A quantifiable outcome occurring randomly. This word has undergone most of an evolution since the theory of probability, since its etymology suggests it being the idea of something happening accidentally. In other words, this is the idea we have cultivated.

OED: A possibility or probability of something happening, often by accident rather than design; luck or fortune.

Etymology: From Old French “cheance” (“accident, luck, fate”), from Vulgar Latin “cadential” (“falling”), from Latin “cadere” (“to fall”)

Probability: A mathematical framework of measuring chances.

OED: The quality or state of being probable; the extent to which something is likely to happen or be the case. It can also refer to a mathematical measure of likelihood, expressed as a number between 0 and 1.

Etymology: From Latin “probabilitas” (“likelihood, credibility”), derived from “probabilism” (“provable, credible”), which comes from “probare” (“to test, to prove”).

Risk: Implies a stake that can be lost (or won), anticipating a good or bad outcome. It seeks to calculate the odds based on known factors, mapping uncertainty to certainty.

OED: The possibility of loss, injury, or other adverse circumstance; exposure to danger or hazard.

Etymology: From French “risqué” (17th century), from Italian “risco” (“danger, peril”), possibly from Latin “resicare” (“to cut off”), referring to a hazardous outcome.

Uncertainty: A lack of knowledge as in being the opposite of certainty.

OED: The state of being uncertain; the quality of being indeterminate, unknown, or unpredictable.

Etymology: From Old French “incertainté” (14th century), from Latin “incertus” (“not sure, not fixed”), from *in-* (“not”) + “certus” (“sure, settled, determined”).

Randomness: A lack of predictability in events, pattern, or outcomes. The etymological root of speed suggests being associated with quickly coming out of nowhere but also the spinning a teetotum or a wheel of fortune. Randomness remains unpredictable and unquantifiable but does not necessarily stem from chaos and can be within a system.

OED: The quality of lacking a definite plan, purpose, or pattern; the state of being unpredictable or haphazard.

Etymology: From Middle English “randon” (“impetuous speed, force, violence”), from Old French “randir” (“to gallop, run”), of Germanic origin, related to “rant” and “run”, later meaning “without definite aim.”

Chaos: A lack of order. Just like a random shape Chaos is not quantifiable.

OED: A state of complete disorder and confusion; originally, a formless void or primordial state of the universe.

Etymology: From Latin “chaos”, from Greek “khaos” (“abyss, vast empty space”).

Luck: A personal experience of fortune and reward closely linked to dopamine, whether unexpected or anticipated, but not stemming from one’s own actions.

OED: Success or failure apparently brought by chance rather than one’s own actions; good or bad fortune.

Etymology: From Middle Dutch “luc” (“happiness, good fortune”), of uncertain origin, possibly related to “gelucke” (Dutch) and “Glück” (German, meaning “fortune, good luck”).

A. FRAMEWORK OF REFERENCE

3. DIVINATION

DIVINATION AS A CONSULTATIVE INSTITUTION

Cicero offers a definition of divination in his work *De Divinatione* (c. 44 BCE/1942) as being the “interpretation of signs or messages from the Gods” or “the foresight and knowledge of the future” (Book I.1.) which remains widely accepted, with Encyclopedia Britannica pointing out that modern scholars no longer restrict the word to the root meaning of coming from Gods but a broader “consultative institution” (...) “universally concerned with practical problems, private or public, and seeks information upon which practical decisions can be made.”⁵ For example an illness or a lost object. So, the intention of divination is to seek answers or some sort of truth – or shall we say certainty – which is a different intention from the uncertainty and excitement we seek in play.

A mantis or a diviner, from the Greek word “μάντις”, functions as a private practitioner across the globe whether for medicinal advice, fortune-telling, or soothsaying, being a seer, medium or prophet. A mantis is the communicator to the divine or its credible interpreter and the consultative institution with trust rested in her/him. However, a mantis’s authority was seldomly based on a purely belief of divine origin but was dependent on societal reputation. Herodotus describes how the Scythian king always asked three diviners when ill, like one may consult multiple doctors. If one was accused of wrong, then two more were brought in. If in the end it was proven or not proven, either the accused or the accusers got beheaded. (Herodotus, c. 440 BCE/1920, 4.68) Since accusations could backfire, diviners had a game-theoretic incentive to agree among colleagues, growing an institution of experts that would not hurt one another’s status. Cicero jokes if multiple diviners looking inside a liver for answers don’t have to burst out laughing, having to admit of simply making it all up (Cicero, c. 44 BCE). Among some Native American tribes Frederick Hodge describes how a payment might be returned by a mantis if the response turned out to be inaccurate or be severely punished if showing any bias towards a certain outcome (Hodge 1975, p.522).

The main quality of a mantis is therefore to be without bias as well as providing accurate results while one’s high status of wisdom is subject to a significant amount of social pressure as a consultative institution. Therefore, while divination seekers look for answers and

⁵ Encyclopædia Britannica. (n.d.). Divination. In *Encyclopædia Britannica Online*. Retrieved February 3, 2025, from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/divination>

certainty, a mantis is well off to safeguard her/himself by being only a messenger between an unbiased source and providing answers with an interpretative stage that could later be fit to the results. Typically, the answer was said to rest within the seeker from the beginning.

To prove no bias, a mantis would often resort to ILINX by actively seeking an intoxicated, disoriented or dream-like state, to intentionally reduce as much human AGENCY as possible and letting go of a persona bound by wishes and desires, to receive hidden messages from the spirit world. We know of the Pythia at Delphi from around 800 BCE, the times of Homer, who the word μαντις is mostly associated with. An intoxicated female medium for Apollo that was then carefully translated by a priesthood to provide double-edged answers tailored to personal fears or desires of the seeker that could be interpreted both ways. Like famously telling king Croesus before going to war against the Persian Empire, that a great empire will fall, which in the end turned out to be his own. Divination seekers therefore set in motion one's path to destiny exactly because of seeking it.

The Greek word “μαντεία” means divination, oracle, or prophecy, which was adopted in Latin as “manteia”. Hence the English suffix “-mancy” means "divination by". In antiquity, various divination practices used this suffix. Early examples include the "Νεκρομαντεῖον" a temple to communicate with the dead, mentioned by Herodotus in *Histories* (Herodotus, c.440 BCE/2003). But also, hydromancy (divination by water), chiromancy (reading of palms), pyromancy (fire divination), gastromancy (interpreting stomach sounds), or oneiromancy (dream interpretation).

Some scholars (Amandry, 1950, Johnston, 2008) suggested that there were actually two rites at Delphi: Since the Pythia divined prestigious omens only once per month and could not be afforded by anyone, lot oracles using beans were performed on a daily basis for more trivial matters. Cleromancy (κληρομαντεία), divination by lots, was however first mentioned only by Byzantine theologian John of Damascus in his *Exposition of the Orthodox Faith* (c. 733 CE) – about 1000 years later – concerning discussions on pagan practices that the Christian church had weeded out. Dubbing the whole practice of casting lots all together as cleromancy served a special purpose to distance itself both from pagan divination practices like the Astraglomanteion, but also Jewish ones.

“Cleromancy” was used to clearly distance itself from its Hebrew and pagan roots which is especially noteworthy since casting lots had been personally commanded by God in the Old Testament to allow the Israelites to inquire of him this way⁶. In the Hebrew Tanakh the people of Israel had likewise attempted to rid its people of all kinds of divination and magic of surrounding people not to upset God, like astrology, necromancy, or haruspices (Deuteronomy 18:10-12). And in *De Divinatione* Cicero had tried to rid the Roman people of all superstition to replace it with reason. The only practice he respected was Augury, the observation of eagle flights, because he thought it was a cultural institution that best symbolized the empire. (Book II, p. 451) This is the flip side of divination: Not being a consultative, but a cultural institution. Throughout Western history ritualistic institutions have been moved into a cultural waste bin that was labeled divination or magic.

The Chinese word for divination is 占 (zhān) and includes traditions like astrology (占星) or the I Ching divination (占筮). While attitudes toward these practices have varied over time – like Confucian scholars criticizing certain forms of divination as superstition, especially when used for personal gain or going against state ideology – they were never systematically suppressed in the same way the term divination was used in Abrahamic traditions. Instead, they remained embedded in Chinese cultural history (Pankenier, 2013).

When Christianity – not Cicero’s rationalism – would become the dominant force of the Roman empire it was set on ridding it of pagan ritual – continuing what Deuteronomy had commanded in the Old Testament – and Europe would remain like this for a millennia of the church’s intellectual dominance. But in Renaissance Europe everything that had been sorted out into the waste bin labeled as divination or pagan ritual, was the content that Heinrich Cornelius Agrippa sought to systematically categorize in scholarly fashion of the European enlightenment period. His *Three Books of Occult Philosophy* (1533) were published in Latin in a detailed attempt to categorize the vast array of divinatory and occult practices of both the classical and Renaissance era. In antique fashion the naming of the divinatory source and adding the suffix “-mancy” was used. But “cleromancy” does not appear in English until *The Discovery of Witchcraft* (Scot, 1584). Only during the Romantic movement of the late 18th and mid 19th century occurred a broader occult revival and interest in esotericism, which turned away from the strict rationality of the Enlightenment period to rediscover emotions,

⁶ By Urim and Thummim – Investigated in detail in the historical section on page 79.

nature, and mystical knowledge. Especially occultists like Eliphas Lévi sought to further organize divination methods with *The History of Magic* (Lévi, 1860/2001). But around the same time the new field of anthropology also began to study the rituals, beliefs, and spiritual practices of non-Western cultures. The “-mancy” terminology was therefore appealing due to its simplicity for both occultists and anthropologists alike, with anthropologists often focusing on commonalities among different cultures.

With *Primitive Culture* (1871) E. B. Tylor laid the groundwork for the academic field of anthropology and promoted a comparative method to identify universal patterns and proposed a unilinear cultural evolution with societies progressing from savagery to barbarism and finally to civilization. His major theory was animism, which proclaimed that early cultures believed that spirits inhabit natural objects and phenomena, while attributing supernatural meaning to seemingly random events. Tylor observed that in some cultures people believed that the result of casting lots was not just random chance but an expression of a supernatural will, which he ties into his distinction between “will” (a personal intent) and “shall” (an external obligation or decree) (p. 78). In this context, casting lots was seen to reveal what “shall” happen, meaning an outcome dictated by divine forces or fate, rather than human choice. However, I argue that - in the case of casting lots - this external obligation may first and foremost stem from communal pressure of upholding rules in SACRED EARNEST not necessarily from a belief in a divine power. If a community decides to draw lots on a decision it is as if the whole community has made it together, much like Victor Turner describes the dynamics of common rituals which foster cohesion in what he has called “communitas” in *The ritual process: Structure and anti-structure*. (Turner, 1969)

Spinning a coconut within a group setting has also been documented by E.B. Tylor and made him position divination and playing with chance close together as he observed a group doing it for entertainment but also for litigation purposes, like finding a perpetrator, with the latter being accompanied by prayers and enchantments. (Tylor, 1871, p.80) So, Tylor himself described the tribal mind being perfectly able to distinguish between play and ascribing higher meaning to it, not seeing the workings of Gods behind every movement but rather entering a different social commitment, a different Magic Circle with a different SACRED EARNEST. Just like we know that making a cross to vote for officials is different than crossing something off a shopping list or documenting a hit when playing battleships. It is the same underlying technique, just a different meaning depending on the social setting.

THE TERMINOLOGY PROBLEM

The problem is that a categorization by object or material as the divinatory source is highly insufficient if not entirely counterproductive. The “-mancy” terminology provides both features of appearing scientific suitable for categorizing as well as ridiculing a practice for superstition.

Rhabdomancy, or “Rhabdomanteia” for example comes from Greek “ῥάβδος“ (rhabdos) a rod, but first appears in English in 1646 in Thomas Browne’s *Pseudonomia Epidmeica*, a more humorous scientific work about debunking prevalent superstitious practices, where a common use of wooden sticks - usually forked - was to search for natural resources like water. But when the I Ching is used with sticks it is sometimes also referred to as a sort of rhabdomancy, even though the methods and intentions are very different. The same goes for “psephomancy” the supposed divination using pebbles (psephos). Despite its classical appearance and a possible use of the most ancient origins due to the abundance of pebbles in nature, it does not appear until 1727 in OED's dictionary (Bailey, 1727).

“Plastronomy” and “Scapulomancy” have a lot in common since they both use relatively flat bones into which symbols are carved. They are then thrown into the fire until they crack. But we could easily file them both under “Pyromancy” (divination with fire) claiming fire to be the divinatory source. But we could also call it “Osteomancy” (divination with bones), which however mostly refers to the analysis of bones after consumption, which represents more of the 20th century appearance of “Tasseomancy”, from the French word “tasse” for “cup”, which is divining from leftovers in a cup like coffee grounds or other sediments of the preferred drink like tea or wine. But “Astragalomancy” could also be filed under “Osteomancy” as well as under “Cleromancy”, since astragals are both bones as well as being used as lots. Just like most forms of “Rhabdomancy” and “Belomancy” (divination with arrows) qualify as lots, when used for drawing or shaking them out of a quiver.

The key takeaway is that one can divine from literally anything since it is appealing to the human imagination to interpret random patterns just like Rorschach inkblots are used for psychoanalysis by applying ink to a sheet of paper which is then folded to create symmetrical, mirror-image patterns. Connecting dots, finding patterns, solving riddles, is incredibly pleasing to our brain as discussed in the neuroscience section on pages 23-34.

CLEROMANCY

Methods of divination, such as the Chinese I Ching, the Ifá of Yoruba, the Greek Astragalomanteion or the Roman Sortes Sanctorum are all described as "cleromancy" and share a lot of common characteristics. It would however be more accurate to call them "clero-literae-mancy" since it is merely the source that is generated by lots and chance, which then references a verse⁷, an abstract symbol or a piece of scripture, which is the basis for interpretation. In other words, the lot alone does not generate the answer and a purely numerical outcome by chance would show to be highly unsatisfactory.⁸ In the example of Shona divination for example the lots don't point to a symbol, but the symbols themselves are marked on both sides of the 4 binary lots, which can generate 16 possible outcomes. But the overall similarities raise the question if what is dubbed cleromancy is even possible without any interpretative stage of abstract symbols or scripture. What is one left with before the creation of scripture other than a random decision-making mechanism?

Some abstract form is necessary as a source for an interpretative stage, and for that abstract symbols, runes or scripture are necessary. Walter Ong pointed out the distinction between classical anthropologists studying people of oral traditions, while sociologists study people within literal societies. However, he points out that both had failed to consider the effects of literacy itself on human thought in his book *Orality and Literacy: The Technologizing of the Word* (Ong, 1982). Apart from the revolution from pictural symbols to phonetic symbols, a different use in mediums of clay tablets, bamboo slips or papyrus scrolls is noteworthy: Only since the 1st and 2nd century AD would pages of a bound book be „flipped” instead of using a scroll. This form of compiling scripture, known as a codex, has taken place in the Roman empire (Roberts & Skeat, 1983). In China on the other hand, writing had traditionally been done on strips of bamboo, that were later tied together to form mats that could be rolled up. While the format of a paper-based book provided a later format of random selection, the Chinese format originally allowed for random drawing of marked bamboo slips (Needham, 2008). I therefore suggest that most practices named cleromancy represent objects of thought that were playfully cast or rearranged within a media revolution of symbols and scripture. Underneath it however had been the long-established cultural techniques of casting lots.

⁷ Ifa divination does not use scripture but generates 1 of 256 (2⁸) options that are remembered by the priest.

⁸ It is imperative to make a pop-cultural reference to *The Hitchhiker's guide to the Galaxy* (Adams, 1979) Where a supercomputer is asked for the answer to "life, the universe and everything" only to come up with the unsatisfying answer of 42.

To highlight a difference of use, while the I Ching or Ifa use a longer and more ritualistic method, which requires multiple casts to generate a code of lines, the development of cleromancy in the Western world can be characterized by a growing corpus of scripture and a quicker way to access it randomly, by using merely a single cast or a random poke.

Before six-sided dice established themselves within the Graeco-Roman realm, the Greek “Astragalomanteion” used 5 Astragals (Talus bones of sheep) to roll a number between 5 and 30 providing 24 different possible outcomes⁹ (with varying probability) that would direct to a certain letter of the alphabet, which was connected to a specific oracle (Heinevetter, 1912). The Roman successor, the “Sortes Sanctorum”, used 3 throws of 6-sided dice, giving 6^3 , therefore 216 possible answers to point to a verse of which several oracles derived from the Astragalomanteion. However, the names of the pagan Gods had already been changed to the Christian one (Tibaldini, 2023 p.48) with its title being a reference to Colossians 1:12. The earliest surviving example is a Greek fragment of Christian origin from the 4th or 5th century with the texts later being revised to align better with church teaching. By the time the text had been translated into Latin, the Council of Vannes (465 CE) had condemned its use along with the “Sortes Biblicae”, which was a widespread use of randomly picking the bible either by hand or with a blade. Christians were seeking revelations about the life of Jesus Christ as prophesies believed to be already foretold within the Old Testament. It was eventually condemned by the church as superstition or improper use of sacred texts even though this seeking of a typology made up a good part of how the New Testament was created in the first place.¹⁰

It was condemned as part of a wider effort to ban the use of chance in general as pagan practices like sortition for the election of officials, since in a deterministic philosophy nothing could happen by chance¹¹. As mentioned on page 35, the term “κληρομαντεία” (cleromancy), was then first used by Byzantine theologian John of Damascus (c. 733 CE). All these practices involve picking a verse by chance, but since the source-object of the “Sortes Biblicae”¹² was a book and not a lot, it would much later be called “bibliomancy”.

⁹ The numbers 6 and 29 are impossible to roll with the Greek numbering of the sides being 1-3-4-6.

¹⁰ See historical analysis on page 90-95.

¹¹ See historical analysis on page 94 - Augustine of Hippo in *City of God* (ca. 413–426/2009)

¹² See historical analysis on page 93.

I CHING

The I Ching (易经) or Zhou Yi (周易) is called the “book of changes” and was compiled during the early Western Zhou Dynasty (c. 1046–771 BCE). At this stage it functioned primarily as a manual for divination used by the ruling elite. (Smith, 2012) The contemporary method is done by flipping three coins to generate a code, but this was not recorded until as late as around 1000 AD after coins had become more widespread. The coin method is faster and mathematically more equal in outcomes than the traditional method using 50 yarrow stalks based on early Chinese numerology.

The I Ching certainly qualifies as divination. In the end one is presented with poetry of old wisdom in one of the 64 chapters of the book of changes which one can then interpret according to one's current state of mind. One can do it alone or seek a professional who knows the rules of the ritual. But one does not simply open a book at random or casts a roll of dice or astragals which then points to a verse. Instead, one is going through a process that takes a little bit of time but also keeps one's mind quite engaged and focused in a very meditative and playful way. The I Ching incorporates a much more living tradition, mixing elements of divination, mathematics, meditation, culture, and play. While much has been written about the internal mathematics of the I Ching and how much understanding for odds and probabilities it already encompassed 3000 years ago, I only want to give the briefest overview to demonstrate its mechanics and MEANINGFUL PLAY:

Both methods have the same interpretation of the resulting numbers. Using coins, Heads or Tails are assigned either the numbers 2 or 3, while using stalks the smaller or larger piles are assigned 2 or 3. In total 3 flips or stalk-piles are generated and always add up to either 6, 7, 8 or 9. The even numbers then represent Yin with a broken line (---) while uneven numbers represent Yang with a solid line (—). However, only 7 and 8 are considered “stable lines” while 6 and 9 are called "changing lines", which will ultimately transform into the other: Yin (---) into Yang (—) and vice versa. This change may not seem reasonable but marks the exciting part. While the odds are the same in the modern coin method, in the traditional one, they are only equal until completing the first Hexagram, but after the final change the overall odds are in favor of Yin with 10/16 against Yang with 6/16.

- 6 (2+2+2) → Changing Yin (---) → (—) 1/8 vs. 1/16
- 7 (3+2+2) → Stable Yang (—) 3/8 vs. 5/16
- 8 (3+3+2) → Stable Yin (---) 3/8 vs. 7/16
- 9 (3+3+3) → Changing Yang (—) → (---) 1/8 vs. 3/16

The goal of the I Ching is to complete one of 64 possible hexagrams 卦 (guà), a combination of six lines, either solid or broken. Without any necessary knowledge of how the process works, I would like to guide the reader through this process without thinking too much about the details just to illustrate its playful difference to simply rolling dice:

One starts with 50 yarrow stalks. There is a ritualistic start by singling out 1 stalk onto which the 3 results of piles are then laid upon as if providing a game board. Then each “level” starts with a random division of the remaining 49 stalks, and another ritualistic start of counting. Again 1 stalk is singled out, which now requires a little bit of dexterity since it is put between the fingers of the hand one holds a bundle in. It is said that this opens the world to the divine, but it also makes the mathematical model work underneath, so that the results always add up correctly. One is then in a process of always sorting out exactly 4 stalks, which demands slight concentration. In the first level one must remember to sort out the 1 stick but in the other two it is counted as well. If one does not end up with either 4 or 8 one has the feedback that one did something wrong and must start this level over again. Each level goes a bit faster since more stalks are already sorted out. After 3 times of shuffling and sorting one can then calculate the result of Yins and Yangs and add them all up to draw the first line. A first pleasing finish line. All of this is then repeated 6 times until one has completed the Hexagram. But then - just before the end - everything changes! All the old Yins and Yangs switch, and one can draw up a completely different Hexagram. This is MEANINGFUL PLAY. In the end one’s mind is a bit fresher; one is guided to the page in the book and is rewarded with a poem, about a bridge that one is advised not to cross, but only those who do cross will ever know (or something of that sort). One can then reflect on what that means for oneself in that moment in time and perhaps make personal choices. Being either reinforced in one’s belief to be wise and not cross a bridge, or believe it is telling one to make a leap of faith. Whether one truly believes in its divine power of revealing hidden truths is secondary. It is a personal experience but also divination as a cultural tradition. And as such it is respected. (Erkes, 1945)

Sinologist Joseph Needham theorized that early Chinese sortition with sticks could have involved quivers before yarrow stalks became standardized (Needham, 2008) and that the I Ching may have been preceded by simpler forms like Kau Chim (求籤) known as "Chinese fortune stick drawing", a traditional method of divination practiced in Chinese temples where sticks are inscribed with a number to point to a corresponding verse and were drawn or shaken out of a quiver until one falls out. See figure 2 on page 52.

SHAKING THE QUIVER

Shaking a quiver of long staffs or rods suggests being related to a quiver of arrows, but in a standardized format of equal length and without any arrowheads or feathers to prevent interlocking. According to the prevalent terminology this would be belomancy (using arrows) or rhabdomancy (using sticks). It is conceivable that the origin of these practices stems from the worldwide standard hunting equipment, a quiver of arrows. Tribes of hunters worldwide certainly used this equipment apart from its primary function for various playful purposes or tribal rituals to give it a different - and at times higher - meaning.

Hisham ibn-al-Kalbi (737 CE - 819 CE) describes a practice of divination arrows within the Ka'bah of pre-islamic times, where an idol with a golden hand called Hubal stood from which people sought answers from. His descriptions are so clear that the whole can be cited:

"It stood inside the Ka'bah. In front of it were seven divination arrows (sing, qidh, pi. qidah or aqduh). On one of these arrows was written "pure" (sarih), and on another "consociated alien" (mulsag). Whenever the lineage of a new-born was doubted, they would offer a sacrifice to it [Hubal] and then shuffle the arrows and throw them. If the arrows showed the word "pure," the child would be declared legitimate and the tribe would accept him. If, however, the arrows showed the words "consociated alien," the child would be declared illegitimate and the tribe would reject him. The third arrow was for divination concerning the dead, while the fourth was for divination concerning marriage. The purpose of the three remaining arrows has not been explained. Whenever they disagreed concerning something, or purposed to embark upon a journey, or undertake some project, they would proceed to it [Hubal] and shuffle the divination arrows before it. Whatever result they obtained they would follow and do accordingly." (Ibn al-Kalbi, 1952, p.22)

It is a clearly divinatory intention to reveal hidden knowledge, like if a child is from one's tribe or not. We know the arrows had writing on them to give very specific answers for very specific questions or issues, concerning family matters, of lineage, whether it be a child's origin, marriage, or deceased relatives. On the other hand, it was also about making decisions about disagreements or which direction to go.¹³ But we know of the underlying technique that the quiver was shaken, and arrows were cast (thrown) out of it randomly that had certain answers written on them.

¹³ The pre-islamic against Islamic traditions concerning arrow divination are discussed in the historical analysis on the pages 96-98.

It has strong parallels with a line in the Tanakh (Old Testament) where it says “For the king of Babylon stands at the parting of the way, at the head of the two ways, to use divination. He shakes the arrows (emphasis added by author); he consults the teraphim; he looks at the liver. (Ezekiel 21:21) and depending on the translation it will say “He will cast lots with arrows” (NIV) or “He shook the arrows back and forth” (HNV) or “They cast lots by shaking arrows from the quiver” (NLT).

When in search for divination using lots without any writings, we may turn to the Germanic practices described by Tacitus in *Germania* (Tacitus, c. 98 CE, chapter 10) which are often claimed to be rune casting, but the earliest runes were only located around 150 AD (Barnes, 2012)¹⁴. Tacitus tells of the Germanic people that „Auspicia et sortes“, the observation of birds and sortition, were highly honored among them with sortition working in a simple matter of picking branches from a tree, marking them with signs (not necessarily writing or runes) and randomly scattering them over a white cloth. Then, while looking up to the heavens and saying a prayer, the priest picked up three and interprets the outcome. If the sortes prohibit any action the consultation ends, but if they permit it, then he looks to augury – the birds – for further guidance.

The interpretation appears to be very crude as in Yes or No, permitting or prohibiting. And the questions that Tacitus suggests were mostly concerning military matters, if a tribe should go to war or not, which again appears to be stepping in tradition with many other cultures of that time. In these instances, a decision is outsourced, and quite often very big ones. But does that qualify as divination? What hidden knowledge is revealed? I argue that it does not qualify as divination anymore but that it is merely a cultural institution mimicking it. Instead, it is much more plausible that it emerged out of an even more ancient practice to make communal decisions among pre-literary societies. I would reframe E.B. Tylor’s differentiation between “will” and “shall” into a differentiation between outsourcing a decision to the divine and divination to reveal from the divine. Having stood the test of time to reach an institutional stage upheld in SACRED EARNEST, casting lots represents an archetypical play element of culture.

¹⁴ "The earliest datable runic inscription is generally taken to be that on the Vimose comb from Denmark, which can be placed around 150 AD." (Barnes, 2012, p. 3).

SUMMARY DIVINATION

Divination seeks to reveal hidden knowledge from the uncertainty, which is a fundamental part of life, like the future. Compared to the intentional uncertainty of play, the divinatory intention therefore seeks some sort of answers or certainty. Its methods or sources however can at times be described as playful since literally anything can be used for divination if divination is actively sought instead of merely interpreting natural phenomena as random omens. A mantis serves as a communicator between the divine and the profane while randomness can provide legitimacy for coming from an unbiased and external source to be interpreted as otherworldly.

An interpretative stage in general is necessary for divination, and if it also provides measurable feedback that can be compared, a typology of knowledge can be compiled. If the outcome is a random pattern like a splatter of paint, the remains of coffee or how objects come to rest in relation to one another, it provides enough flexibility for interpretation. The pure outcome of chance however will always be a numeral and must further point to an abstract idea, symbol or piece of scripture that can provide this interpretative stage. Therefore, cleromancy mostly required the thought and media revolution of applying meaning to abstract symbols like scripture.

Divination is also used to describe a cultural institution of common ritual but also as superstition when used to separate a cultural superiority over others, like Christians condemning pagan ritual as such. Most divination terminology using the suffix “-mancy” stems from a renewed interest in antique sources during Renaissance Europe and was widely adopted during an interest in the occult of 19th century Europe as well as the young field of anthropology during the same time, which sought common patterns among all cultures. However, simply describing the source of divination is flawed since it tells little about its use. Most influential literature of game studies cites E.B. Tylor (1871), a founding father of anthropology, but his loose differentiation between “will” and “shall” concerning the use of lots for either divination or play is very vague and in need of clarification.

JUXTAPOSITION

Diagram 2

DECISION VS. PLAY

A decision seeks and requires certainty. Play seeks uncertainty for excitement. There are personal decisions and there are group decisions. We play alone or we can play in groups. However, for the most part of human history games required multiple people¹⁵. We can simply decide, and we can also simply play in terms of PAIDIA. It is both voluntary. But to play games (LUDUS) we must first decide to play and mutually agree to uphold our common rules. This requires a decision on each part to leave their own reality for the time being. Within a game we can make many decisions within the framework of rules, where we can use our AGENCY with AGÔN or MIMICRY or give it up with ALEA or ILINX. But all decisions ultimately require or have AGENCY to be able to follow through. “In games as in life, the purpose of information is to influence choice. If you have no choice, there’s not much point in being informed.” (Parlett, 2018, p.20-21) Lastly, with absolute certainty about the game the game itself ends. We could however play rock-paper-scissor to decide who is then allowed to decide the course of the evening. But a decision always brings certainty.

PLAY VS. DIVINATION

While uncertainty is a common trait in play as in life, play seeks uncertainty for excitement. Divination on the other hand uses it as an unbiased source to seek answers. Divination typically only has one seeker for a very personal spiritual answer, but although one can easily play alone for joy, playing games (LUDUS) typically has many playing parties in interaction with each other in a common social contract. The interpretation of outcomes in divination is typically left to one party alone, either the mantis or the seeker (or both, but only in consecutive order). Divination requires some kind of interpretative stage, while playing games does not. To the contrary an interpretative stage - especially concerning rules - is highly frustrating for the flow of a game, mostly if it must be negotiated between several participants. A clear numeral on how many fields one must move is preferable. For divination the unbiased externality is practical as a divine source as far removed from a human bias as possible, while for play it provides equal fairness to the excitement of uncertainty.

¹⁵ Before digital gaming, the average ludic experience required multiple players. With rare exceptions (e.g solitaire).

DIVINATION VS. DECISION

The main difference between divination and decision-making is whether one truly possesses the AGENCY of the outcome. Flipping a coin to ask if one should go left or right is simply seeking a decision. One could go either left or right on one's own if one just makes up one's mind. However, if one flips a coin to ask if a child being born will be a boy or a girl, that is divination, since one has absolutely no control over the child's sex. It remains hidden information (before the invention of x-ray) that only the future can show to be right or wrong. In this sense a differentiation between "will" and "shall" is also made, but it is exactly the opposite of E.B. Tylor's and not concerning play vs. divination but vs. making decisions. The intention can be differentiated if one gains certainty or mere answers as basis for interpretation. Divination is trusted to reveal hidden knowledge as a basis for personal decision making, but not to make the decision itself.

Concerning the external decision by the flip of a coin as it is done for example at the start of a soccer match to decide which team kicks off first, no hidden knowledge is divined. One could use AGÔN in discussion or with a higher authority to make that choice, but this would be subject to bias. One rather chooses to save time and energy to decide on what must be done with the outcome being irrelevant. The same goes for sortition among a group of people who is to take out the trash. Nobody wants to do it on an equal level and refuses, nevertheless somebody must do it. If nobody volunteers or no higher authority is present, like a parent to pick someone, the group can resort to drawing lots to make an unbiased decision. Since they are doing it among equals, the outcome is irrelevant. It is commonly referred to as a tiebreaker.

But how does that compare to outsourcing grand decisions to lots like going to war or not? It is easy to argue about using lots to make an impartial decision among equal options. But clearly risking thousands of lives or staying home are not equal options, and the outcome is far from irrelevant. Yet, across cultures this has been widely documented for military leaders or communities to outsource this decision.¹⁶ We must acknowledge that in all these examples they still possess the AGENCY to decide for themselves by arguing or voting, but no hidden knowledge is revealed. It can be a cultural and consultative institution that mimics the likes of divination with ritual. Nevertheless, it is a choice to resort to an unbiased group decision.

¹⁶ Multiple instances are discussed in the historical analysis of p. 81-88

CULTURAL AMBIGUITY

These clear intellectual distinctions and juxtapositions can be easily separated by philosophical discourse aided by a common scripture to formulate ideas and common definitions. However, this does not necessarily matter within a cultural setting with ideas being easily intertwined by association, like anthropologists would observe. As military decisions of grandeur were typically accompanied with great ritual importance it is easy to claim that everybody simply believed “the Gods” decided, and that they were all filled with superstition. But I argue it was honoring (whether consciously or not) a tradition of making a communal decision, being a cultural institution grown out of a playful act that proved to be of enormous civilizing value by generating unbiased decisions.

While we have no exact idea about our ancestors' intentions and the meaning of words can change over time, we can only analyze the characteristics of their practices and make educated deductions if no other information is provided. But we are not honoring our cultural ancestors' by ascribing an inherent superstition to their intentions, but rather hinder our future research by lacking clearer definitions. To the contrary, merely labeling practices as divination if prayers were uttered, not only carries along a stigma of being primitive compared to civilized. But if we would have to end the conclusion right here then games of chance must have never evolved out of divination methods until today. Whenever one yells out “Oh my God!” while observing or playing a game in a moment of tension and suspense, we would have no right to distinguish one from another with, despite all our modern knowledge of probability.

David Parlett writes that “It seems more reasonable to regard lot-casting as a generalized activity that has always been employed seriously, curiously or playfully, according to the temperament and circumstance” (2018, p. 21). This is agreed with, as this thesis perceives casting lots as a general cultural technique. However, with this structured framework of juxtapositions we can analyze very distinct characteristics between different kind of lots and locate their specific uses on a spectrum of use cases.

ILLUSTRATIONS

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

The magic of arrows and quivers

Left: Shaking a quiver of marked arrows may have been a primal form of a lottery among bands of hunters for unbiased selection and distribution. Giving up the agency of the individual to the ritual of the group can forge a strong sense of „communitas“ (Turner, 1969)

Right: The evolution into standardized staves within a quiver as used for early Chinese games and divination like the I Ching.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Quantifiable outcomes vs. interpretative stages

Numerals have existed before the invention of more complex abstract symbols or scripture necessary for divinatory interpretation. Dice with numerals primarily serve play, while inscribed dice were originally used for secular decision-making like assigning mandates.

Left: Die of the Indus Valley dating back to 2500 - 1900 BCE.

Right: Yaḥalu's pūru, a decision die of Assur to assign official mandates by lot (886 BCE).

A game played together vs. the solitary experience of divination

The game boards of Senet found in Egyptian tombs had originally been empty squares, and only later featured abstract symbols, as scripture gradually developed. It is mostly depicted being played together, opposed to possibly more spiritual uses in solitude. (Piccione, 1980)

Left: Nebemnaʿat playing Senet with his wife Meretseger.

Right: Queen Nefertari playing Senet alone.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Divination as a cultural institution

Haruspices, the interpretation of omens from sheep livers, exemplifies divination not just as a consultancy but also as a long lasting cultural institution. A common interpretation of certain marks were formalized into a common typology as trusted „holy scriptures“.

Left: Clay liver from Babylon used for divination, 2050-1750 BCE.

Right: Etruscan bronze liver of Piacenza ca. 200 BCE.

The deification of chance

The Roman goddess Fortuna was an all-powerful deity in control of chance. At her temples inscribed lots called „Sors“ were drawn from a vessel called „Sitella“. Her rise to a broad institutional role exemplifies Huizinga’s play element of culture.

Left: Roman Denarius (69 BCE) depicting the Sors of Fortuna.

Right: The gigantic temple of Fortuna at Praeneste near Rome.

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

Figure 11.

Figure 12.

The media revolution of scripture in creating objects of thought

Left: With the Roman format of a Codex, the binding of papers within a book instead of scrolls, spread around the the time of early Christianity. It created a lottery format of randomly picking pages, that made bibliomancy possible.

Right: On the contrary, original writing in China had been on bamboo slips later bound into scrolls, inhibiting a lottery format.

OBJECTS USED

Several objects and artifacts were used by the author to analyze and demonstrate the physical and performative qualities firsthand. Objects like the Playmobil® Martin Luther or the molten led piece from an Austrian New Year's Eve tradition "Bleigießen" represent more abstract concepts for differentiation. This small selection should provide a basic overview how lots can be made and used to produce chance.

1. **Random shape** represents intentional **chaos**. It provides a great interpretative stage for divination, but is **unquantifiable**, and does not qualify as a lot.
2. **Scripture**. Pages can be "turned" and "picked" at random from a book as a large poly lot. Writing provides a **common interpretative stage**.
3. **Coins**. Equal binary lots (D2) producing 1 of 2 outcomes by "flipping". Ideal for decision making. But feels awkward to shake in one's hand to cast.
4. **Cowrie shells**. Unequal binary lots naturally found along coastlines. By "shaking" in one's hand and "casting" them they produce a binary code. Using multiples is ideal for gaming.
5. **Astragals**. Unequal 4-sided poly lots found as Sheep bones. Producing 4 unequal outcomes by chance by "casting". Ideal for games.
6. **Cubical die**. Poly lot with 6 equal sides (D6) producing 1 of 6 numerals by chance by "casting". Ideal for games.
7. **Decision die**. Poly lot with 6 equal sides (D6) producing 1 of 6 answers by chance by "casting". Answers questions like "when should/will I ... ?" while giving specific answers of "now", "later", "tomorrow", etc. Necessitates writing and interpretation.
8. **Teetotum**. Poly lot with letters to act upon producing 4 options by chance through the action of "spinning". (Dreidel depicted)
9. **Bag**. Container to be used for unique lots. Hiding the information "shaken" inside causes the randomization which is then "drawn" out.
10. **Marked sticks**. Representative of a possible evolution of using marked **arrows**. Used for lottery by "drawing" or "shaking" out of a container like a quiver or hiding the markings in a hand. They can also be randomly scattered to interpret random patterns for divination or for play.

Figure 13

B. LOTS AS OBJECTS

THE LOT AS AN OBJECT

A lot represents a physical object used to generate a random outcome or intentional uncertainty, with dice representing a specifically crafted sub-category of lots.

The purpose of lots in game design is to provide “imperfect knowledge” (Parlett, 2018) since one does not know the exact outcome of a die roll but is still able to make certain predictions on possible outcomes. We should not confuse this with hidden (or occult) knowledge, which we could symbolize by hiding something under a cloth and letting someone else guess what is beneath it. Without any hints it can only be a wild guess and we could not correctly call those hidden pieces lots since we have no knowledge at all.

We can differentiate three basic lot-types:

1. **Unique lots** like a name on a piece of paper drawn among a given number.
2. **Binary lots** provide two possible outcomes like flipping a coin.
3. **Poly lots** like dice have different sides with multiple fields.

Here are some examples in subcategories of being naturally available or different degrees of craftsmanship (**N** = naturally available; **M** = manipulated or marked; **C** = crafted):

Table 2

	Unique	Binary	Poly
N	Sticks, Stones, Seeds, Bones, etc.	Cowrie Shells	Astragals
M	Marked Sticks, Stones, Seeds, Bones, etc.	Split Sticks, Stones, Seeds, Bones, etc.	Marked Astragals, Vibhitaka seeds
C	Arrows, Lottery balls	Coins	Dice, Teetotums

UNIQUE LOTS

Using unique lots may seem like the simplest of all, but one typically requires a second thing: A container to hide the unique lots. One also typically needs multiple ones which can be differentiated from each other, like different but unique markings or lengths.

A different possibility would be to spin a single object to point into a direction. And lastly to cast a single unique lot in its most crude form like a rock onto a field of different outcomes. In this latter case the field itself represents the lot of multiple unique outcomes onto which a randomizer is cast, like a marble onto a spinning Roulette wheel. Here, the common agreement of the correct method of casting without any bias is more important, while the drawing from a shaken vessel is easier to visually communicate to all participants.

Here are some subcategories of being naturally available or different degrees of craftsmanship (**N** = naturally available; **M** = manipulated or marked; **C** = crafted):

Table 3

	Container	Spinners	Field
N	Hand	Coconut	Cliff
M	Scraped Gourd, Calabash	Rounded or pointed Wood, Stone, etc.	Marked Field, Ground
C	Pot, Bag, Cloth	Wheel of Fortune, Bottle	Cloth, Table, Roulette wheel

A last option is using no object at all, only hands. In this case the lot is purely rule-based.

N	Pure Hand
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PURE HAND GAMES

Hands can hold and hide by forming a fist. Fingers can communicate by pointing and displaying numerals and can also portray abstract symbols if we agree on their meaning. Hand games are often “Von Neumann Games” of classical game theory (Von Neumann, 1944) with each player making a move simultaneously and then comparing the outcome.

Rock - Paper - Scissor is a simple game using only hands to form one out of three options and need two players, who will have all the features of a game of chance.¹⁷ No matter what one picks with one's own AGENCY and decision, one never knows which of the two remaining options the other player picks, therefore making it up to chance if one wins or loses. A pure-strategy equilibrium is impossible since every move is either one to beat or to be beaten. In 1/3 of the cases a draw would occur, so we would have to go again until we reach a conclusion. (1944, p.164) This is ALEA by means of AGÔN and there are quite a couple of rules. It is therefore usually played if two people need a decision between two different interests in outcomes compared to a decision which outcome is irrelevant. Although it can be used for both.

Morra is an Italian game surviving from the Roman times, where it was called *micare digitis*; "to flash the fingers". *Fifteen-Twenty* a Chinese version has been documented in China by poets like Li Bai dating back to the 7th century Tang Dynasty (Li, 2003). On the count of three each player flashes a number of fingers on their hand, while at the same time yelling out a guessed number which should represent the sum of all flashed numbers added together. If someone happens to be correct s/he wins. In *Morra* the dominant strategy will be calling the mean average while guessing the extremes provides one with the least probability to win. If 4 players compete there will be only 1 possibility of having an outcome of either 0 or 20, but 146 possibilities of flashing 10.

Primal hand games would rather be some sort of playful way of inter-locking, clapping, or rubbing since common rules require more conceptualization. But once we add simple objects, we can have simple lotteries like drawing sticks or a binary lottery by hiding an object in one of the two hands and letting a different person pick one hand with a 50:50 chance of being right. This could also be applied for a tiebreaker decision which outcome is irrelevant. I therefore argue that using objects is typically a more straightforward use for lots than developing objects of thought.

¹⁷ It occurred to me if that may be a reason for having 2 and 3 as the basis of the I Ching.

BINARY LOTS

Binary lots, like flipping a coin, offer the simplest way to make impartial decisions like Yes or No, Me or You, Left or Right. Coins are the first true binary lots as actual D2 dice with an equal chance of landing on either side, but the earliest coin-flip can only date to around 600 BCE in Lydia, where the first coins were minted with the intention of being used as money. (Weatherford, 1997) Flipping is a playful use stemming from its physical attributes of being flat, which is rarely found in nature.

Even though the odds can't be exactly equal, naturally available binary lots have been identified as such, like various seeds or shells for example. Likewise, shells appear along bodies of water and feature an intrinsic shape of two distinct sides, a round one and an open one. Cowrie shells feel well in one's hands and make wonderful objects of play, being durable yet light. They were also used as one of the earliest known forms of currency with archaeological evidence suggesting that they were used as such in China during the Shang Dynasty as early as 1200 BCE. Eventually half the world traded these objects spreading over Southeast Asia, India, to Africa, where it remained currency up until the 19th century. (Yang, 2019) Their intrinsic value is not only one of beauty, size and durability, but also as object for play as binary lots. One could use them as dice to gamble and money as a single object. In India they would be called Sozhi and were used for dice as well as cleromantic purposes.

When in need of a numerical outcome binary lots are typically numbered 1 or 0¹⁸ and are then used in multiples for gaming. Intentionally crafted objects are in its simplest form split in some way like sticks or shaped bones, which then likewise provide a flat and curved side. Or more carefully crafted throwing sticks with a convex or concave side found among the oldest board games in Egyptian funerary offerings dating back to c. 3000 BCE (Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2004/2018). Typically, four binary lots were cast to produce a number between 0-4. In Mesopotamia tetrahedral dice (D4) were also used as binary lots with two points being marked, as found in the grave of Puabi in the Royal Cemetery of Ur, dated to around 2600 BCE (Woolley, 1934). Although fine craftsmanship was applied for the specific intention of gaming, and the skills to produce poly-sided dice were available, the idea of cubical dice did not appear to be of any value to early Egyptians.

¹⁸ Even though the I Ching used 2 and 3.

POLY LOTS

ASTRAGALS

The astragalus is the talus bone of hooved animals. They are easy to manipulate, making them ideal for play and have four stable sides (concave, convex, broad, narrow), and their primary use for games can be easily argued.

Astragals have been found in funeral offerings of ancient societies dating back to around 5000 BCE. These cultures, such as those in Çatalhöyük, Jericho and Ain Ghazal, (Haddow, 2015) transitioned from nomadic to settled lifestyles of farming crops and domesticating sheep, goats and cattle while living in mudbrick homes underneath which they also buried their ancestors along with their most valued objects during lifetime, like tools or weapons. So even though these funeral rites give evidence of a new form of spiritual life, the objects that they were buried with are not necessarily of ritual nature. Later funerary offerings of Astragals during Greek and Roman times were predominantly found in children tombs, suggesting their primary use of play. (Phialon, 2022)

They most likely became early favorite toys of stacking or flicking. Around 120 games from the traditions of Mongolian nomadic culture are documented as UNESCO cultural heritage¹⁹. Most however feature skill of flicking, and communities still meet up and join in ritualized gaming competitions among tribes. I suggest that the evolution into astragals as early dice however correlate much more with the creation of games. Egyptians used either four-sided astragals or four binary lots in games as early as 3500 BCE as wall paintings and funeral offerings suggest, having little need to switch to a D6. The later numeration of astragals however does not have assigned numbers from 1-4 but are instead in the range of 1-6. This suggests an interexchange of ideas with cubical dice becoming the ideal format, while astragals probably remained the average person's choice. The numbering in Greek and Roman times is well attested (Schädler, 1996; Kidd, 2017). The less likely outcomes (around 20% chance) on the two convex sides were numbered 1 and 6, while the two concave sides which were more stable to land on (around 80% chance) got 3 and 4 (David, 1962). This makes the distributions of means and extremes resemble a slightly skewed Gauss curve showing a good understanding of probability.

¹⁹ UNESCO. (n.d.). *Mongolian knuckle-bone shooting*. Retrieved February 6, 2025, from <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mongolian-knuckle-bone-shooting-00959>

DICE

Dice are specially crafted objects for casting or rolling to intentionally randomize outcomes. They are marked with dots representing numerals since its inception. Markings with symbols are rare and have only been in development when the earliest six-sided dice were made. The earliest find was made of clay and was discovered in Tepe Gawra (Northern Iraq) dating to around 2500 BCE (Speiser, 1935)²⁰. However, evidence suggests dice were brought from the early Indus Valley civilization which had trade connections with Mesopotamia (Lamberg-Karlovsky, 1972). Several clay dice have been found in the Indus Valley at Mohenjo-daro like the one represented in **Figure 3** (p. 53) from the Harappan period around 2000 BCE by archaeologist John Marshall (1931). He speculated that dice were already used in pairs when finding two of the same size, however most were of different sizes. They were not marked in the same way modern dice are, with opposite sides totaling seven, which makes no difference statistically.

After the height of the Indus Valley civilization cubic dice disappeared there and instead moved along with people migrating eastward to influence the early Vedic culture. Since the first Hindu texts (like the Vedas) dice occupy a common theme and became prominent in the epic of Mahabharata. Cubical dice however did not spread to Egypt until much later. The more common early dice in Mesopotamia were astragals, but the Mesopotamian myths and the Hebrew Tanakh only mention “casting lots” not dice. Only in the 5th century BCE does Herodotus credit the Lydians (who had also invented coins) for inventing dice among many other toys and games – to lighten their mood during a great famine – even though he also mentioned that the Lydians themselves did not claim it as their invention either (Herodotus, 1920, p. 125).

While the East favored cubic dice, it did not become widespread in the West, where binary lots or irregularly shaped astragals remained the standard. Interestingly, later Egyptian, and Roman dice were mostly asymmetrical, and studies of Roman dice show a tendency to favor rolls of 1 or 6, due to space limitations on the larger faces, making scholars believe that it reflected the Roman worldview of fate being controlled by the Gods (Eerkens & de Voogt, 2022). A frustration over this belief was expressed by Cicero as well (as discussed on page 88 in the historical section).

²⁰ Mesopotamians used a sexagesimal (60) numeral system compiled of 6 and 10, due to its great divisibility. While 10 is derived from the fingers at hand, the number 6 remains speculative. 2 x 3 makes it greatly divisible, but I would add to the speculation that perhaps the cubical die has influenced the base of 6 as well.

LONG DICE

Long dice have field edges along their long sides and are rolled along its axis. They are typically made from wood or ivory and cannot rest on their short stumps. Some ends are rounded or pointed to ensure they cannot land on their ends. Most have four sides, though variations exist. A Korean version has five sides, while the “Long Lawrence” has eight edges with four markings for better rolling. (Parlett, 2018)

Along with the oldest cubic dice, long dice have been found in Indus Valley sites with *pasa* being the common Indian term for dice. While early dice from the Epic period (around the time the Mahabharata was written) were simply marked 1-2-3-4, later four-faced long dice ranged from 1 to 6 – like Astragals – used in games like Chaupar (a precursor to Pachisi and Ludo). The dice often displayed different pip markings, including Greek-style 1-3-4-6, showing cultural exchange. A couple of later dice featured missing numbers, such as 2-3-4-6, used for games like Dice Chess. (Parlett, 2018)

TEETOTUM

The teetotum evolved from the long die, designed to be spun instead of cast (Parlett, 2018, p.29). Unlike dice, which tumble and settle, a teetotum spins, stretching the uncertainty before landing on one of its faces. A well-known example is the dreidel, popularized in the 16th century during Hanukkah. Both long dice and teetotums can have any number of sides, but teetotums can also have no sides at all, emphasizing merely the beauty of spinning.

While objects like wheels of fortune or roulettes are similar in being structured in sections providing quantifiable outcomes, the act of spinning a bottle or coconut spun transcends structured chance. A bottle spinning in a circle of six people to select a participant can have a 1-in-6 probability, yet it may stop between two, creating ambiguity. It blends structured chance with randomness yet remains ordered in its motion. Spinning an object on a flat surface is a simple form of randomization but eluding chance.

UNIQUE LOTS

FIELDS

Not only can one use different objects as lots, but one can also cast objects onto a field of outcomes, with the result determined by where they come to rest. It could be a marked field on the ground or a piece of cloth. But the way objects are thrown must ensure no aiming or cheating. We want either a level of ILINX to remove the caster's AGENCY or a system of casting. Just like in the thought experiment at the end of chapter one, one would want to throw without aiming but without missing.

The difference with fields—unless carefully crafted like a roulette wheel—is the possibility of unclear feedback. A field drawn on the ground may result in a lot landing on the line. A spun bottle might point between two people. But perhaps this is the point: less about chance and more about randomness, depending on the design of the field.

Germanic lot casting, as described by Tacitus, fits this example (Tacitus, c. 98 CE, chapter 10) although we should question if they qualify as lots. He describes them as sticks with markings scattered on a piece of cloth, where landing inside or outside the cloth could matter. This creates quantifiable outcomes, yet also allows intuitive interpretation—how objects relate, touch, or overlap. By leaving quantifiable outcomes behind, we leave the realm of chance and enter randomness.

If we skip markings entirely and cast a handful of objects, they can create patterns beyond chance but randomness. Their unpredictable landings give no clear answers, only an interpretative stage, perfect for divination. A cluster of rocks might resemble a star constellation; sticks touching one another might symbolize partnership. Here, we hold the universe in our hands, shaped by imagination. I have not come across any records resembling any documented practice like this, but would like to offer this possibility. Perhaps a raven dropping rocks off an edge does the same. (Heinrich & Smolker, 1991) Simply fascinated by random movement, repeating it to find a pattern.

Randomness is the perfect substance for divination, but chance is something else.

LOTTERY / SORTITION

Lotto became popular in Italy in 1620 as a betting game on which government officials were drawn in "*Il Gioco del Lotto di Genova*" (The Game of Lotto of Genoa) a sortition process of selecting 5 out of 120 eligible candidates for the general council. This sortition process was nothing new to the world but was practiced in the Athenian democracy and early Mesopotamia. Sortition is the common political term and it was probably done since hunter gatherer tribes.

Lotteries can generally be divided into two types:

1. **Exclusive selection** – Only one or several lot(s) need(s) to be unique among many, such as drawing the short end of a stick among many. One simply needs two distinct lot types like black or white stones or long and short sticks.
2. **Distributive selection** – Every lot must be distinct, as in having different names written on a piece of paper and then drawn out of a hat for example.

In an Exclusive selection of one person one can easily calculate one's probability as $1/n$, with n being the denominator as the total number of lots or participants (including oneself). If there are more participants to be exclusively selected, then the numerator changes respectively and the probability decreases.

In a Distributive selection everyone "wins" or gets assigned either a duty or a prize. One can only be inclined to calculate one's probability the same way as above if one has a specific prize in mind, but typically this method is used for assignment in an unbiased and random fashion.

Both methods require the concealment of the lots or at least the relevant information thereof, like the length of a stick. It is imperfect knowledge - one can know the probabilities, but the outcome is intentionally randomized. This process therefore requires one more object apart from the lots - a container.

In the scenario of drawing sticks, the role of the container is taken over by the hand of one person who will lead the ritual. If s/he is part of the selection process s/he will end up with the last lot remaining. If the process is done in this fashion special trust must be laid upon

this ritual leader to be impartial, to mix and to conceal the lots well and not to give any hints towards anyone else, since s/he has perfect knowledge of the distribution of lots.

The more trustworthy process therefore is for everyone to draw lots out of a common container. This container represents the decision of the community as a whole. It is everyone combined without anyone having any authority over it. It is sacred since all are equal under the power of the lot.

If we were to draw the lots out of the container, we must now have the requirement upon the lots that they all feel the same. Different length of sticks will not do, but folded papers work perfectly fine. But before the invention of paper, lots had to be carved onto a piece of clay or onto a piece of wood, and now this would require them to all be shaped the same as well. Collecting seeds or beans of big size seems like an option since they would be of much more similar shape but could be easily carved into. But even carvings could make them distinguishable by texture and if we go beyond our invention of scripture, these markings would be even easier distinguishable in the form of lines, crosses, triangles, etc. A color-coded approach would also soon reach limitations, since colors were merely shades of gray, red, yellow, black, or white for most part of prehistory, and would not be applicable permanently but would always be a process of getting one's hands dirty. Different colors in objects historically mostly meant different materials, with different weights, temperature, or texture, meaning they would all feel different.

Very soon we will conclude that we must get our hands out of the picture and out of this common and sacred container. Allowing for no manipulation - "manus" being the Latin word for hand - is essential for this unbiased ritual. But so is the container. Within it there is the community of equals, shaken together at random. But if we can't draw lots out of it, we must somehow cast lots out of it, and we already know of the practice of shaking a quiver of sticks or arrows. This seems like a widespread possible use, and we find differently marked arrows all over the planet. These markings don't require any form of writing but simply differentiation or ownership.

The idea that arrows were a precursor to playing cards is a theory famously discussed by Stewart Culin, an early ethnographer and historian of games (Culin, 1895). The idea that arrow-based divination and gambling games evolved into *paper-based* equivalents in China might be a bit far-fetched with tiles having already been in use before the card. He notes that

early Asian playing cards featured symbols of arrows, but Culin theorized that playing cards may be traced to practical arrows, bearing cosmical or personal marks. He makes the parallel of a pack of cards standing for the quiver of arrows. Huizinga also mentions Culin observing the similarity between arrows and dice among some Native American tribes and when looking at depictions of what are called American divination arrows, it becomes obvious that they indeed are specifically crafted dice in the form of long pointed teetotums, being shaped to have 4 edges and bear no resemblance in its form or function to the use of arrows for hunting (Culin, 1907). The arrow has the inherent feature of being “cast”, so perhaps it is from this feature that “casting lots” is more frequently used than “drawing lots”.

Surely a lot of culture and magic lies around the arrow, ready to be repurposed in playful and ritualistic ways, but above all it is the container that remains the essential object of a lottery and with some technique of “shaking” we can cast lots out of it. Humanity was originally organizing and finding ways of cooperation in female societies, collecting, and distributing naturally available food before starting to organize male groups for hunting, so “the first cultural device was probably a recipient” (Le Guin, 1988). It can be argued that with containers we started cultivating chance.

SUMMARY OF ANALYZING OBJECTS USED FOR LOTS

Differently shaped objects incorporate different performative actions and different use cases. While unique lots mostly require an additional container, their use for sortition probably provided one of the most ancient uses and benefits for nomadic hunting communities, while poly lots would mostly be applicable for playing games at a later development of settled societies along with binary ones. Pure hand games using randomness require a lot of rule-based cooperation, so cultivating chance would therefore be easier with a distinct visual object. Spinning a coconut, drawing sticks or hiding a rock in one of two hands are simple techniques that can generate primal random decisions.

The use of arrows within quivers and - as an evolved method - long sticks within quivers, is argued to be the most ancient standard use of sortition using lots within a container, whether for exclusive selection or distributive sortition. For the latter, decorative markings on arrows make them distinguishable from one another and points to ownership. A true play element of culture, with sortition being one of the possible early playful uses of arrows besides its function to hunt. This ritual can forge a strong feeling of *communitas* (Turner, 1969) with a common container making all participants equal under the power of the lot. But the widespread use of the term “casting lots” is argued to stem from developing more sophisticated techniques to get rid of as much manipulation as possible by limiting the use of hands. Techniques that would elevate the feeling of *communitas* to a higher level than the profane.

Suitable for divination are only objects that don't generate any definite quantifiable outcome of chance but rather a random result provides an interpretative stage, like interpreting how objects come to land in relation to one another. But it is questioned if these objects can then qualify as lots.

Binary lots are optimal for Yes/No decision making and when used in multiples can be used for gaming like casting four split sticks or cowrie shells, but the creation of the D2 object as in a coin is of much younger origin than a D4 or D6 like dice for gaming. The frequent use of astragals correlates with the invention of cubical dice stemming from India and the number range of six was mostly spread out among dice even when they only featured four faces like long dice.

C. LOTS AS OBJECTS OF THOUGHT

THE DIVISORY LOT

The first narrative literary works of humankind were written during the old Babylonian period (c. 1894 – 1595 BC) like the myth of *Atra-Hasis* (von Soden, 1978) by an unknown author. Here the three primal Gods Anu, Enlil and Enki divide the universe by casting lots out of a bottle, according to the translation of von Soden it reads as follows:

“The gods grasped the bottle by its neck, cast the lot, and divided [the universe].” (p.38)

Anu gets the heavens, Enlil the earth and Enki the waters below²¹. However, we must acknowledge the instance that these Gods were not in control over chance but were themselves subject to it. Division by lot has a much more rational origin story as archaeological and linguistic evidence suggests. The standard way of distributing an inheritance in Assyrian and Babylonian Mesopotamia was to divide the property into parcels and then to assign them to the heirs by lot (with variations when the eldest son was privileged) as stated in *A History of Ancient Near Eastern Law* (Westbrook, 2003). Anne Marie Kitz cites an example of a typical Mesopotamian inheritance case of Imgua (Kitz, 2000) that starts with a survey of the entire property beginning with descriptions of immovable properties of the house(s), then about the surrounding swaths of land until lastly the movable property like animal stock, silver, or carpentry, is surveyed. The portions then being “weighed against one another”, and “paid in exchange” until each portion is agreed upon to be of equal value. Finally, the text is concluded with a series of standardized legal clauses:

79 The heirs of Imgua

80 in full agreement

81 have divided [the inheritance]

82 **by lot** (emphasis by author)

83 and have sworn by the name of the king

84 never to raise claims

85 against one another

...

(Seal 8)

²¹The underworld, similar to later Greek mythology’s Hades and the river Styx.

100 Before Neinurta-nigur
101 In the month of abattu (January/February)
102 the 13th year since
103 Rim-Sin, the king,
104 captured Isin.
(Seal 9) (Kitz, 2000, p 614)

They are clauses as we are used today, a list of witnesses, the name of the local authority, a stipulation against future litigation and the date of the completed transaction. The casting of lots together with an oath, represents the ritual completion like a signature today, making it official that they have divided in full agreements.

But how can we then imagine this division by lot? Kitz points out the concern for fairness since all objects of value are first documented from most to least valuable and then weighed against one another. Their value is therefore determined in comparison to one another. They are then exchanged from one part to the other until all parts are considered to be of equal value. Let us imagine five brothers having to divide an inheritance into five equal parts who would document two houses on a property with a river, some arable farmland, a large forest, some rocky hills, 30 units of milk producing livestock like sheep, 20 pots of harvested goods and lastly some shekels of silver (used for weighing and later as currency). Access to water from the river will be of value to all, but the three parts without a house would therefore be eligible for more land of which the arable land would be of more value than the forest which would be worth more than rocky hills. Lastly one could ease the edges and give some parts of less value more of the moveable goods.

But the genius part is that in order to ensure all five parts to be equal the final distribution will be done at random, therefore making it everyone's best interest to first agree on making all parts of equal value, since no one would want to risk having less than the others. This ritual to externalize the decision to the lot therefore puts pressure on the community to come to a mutual understanding of value and an agreement of equality.

But equal value does not mean equal characteristics. For example, being allotted arable land would most likely make one and one's later family farmers, while water access might turn them into fishermen, and swaths of forest into hunters. This would be "one's lot" in life as well as the basis for further subdivision down generations and further inheritance partitions.

The Akkadian word for lot is "puršu" (𒍪𒍪 in cuneiform) also meaning decision, duty, portion, share as well as fate. But the gravity of one's lot in life would probably only start with a division of land among settled agrarian societies with property rights, while dividing shares of a hunted animal might be simply one's lot for dinner. It is easy to imagine a group of hunters who used to live more egalitarian, using this technique to divide hunted game with this technique by shaking a quiver until a marked arrow fell out. I argue that it was one of the most primal cultural techniques with division by lot probably being a long-established institution for eons with the average person knowing the practice of casting lots from childhood. It would be a pre-literate institution just like learning to write one's signature in literate societies, being the binding word, one must stand by.

But even though being the first literate societies, the large part of the population was mostly illiterate as cuneiform writing is made up of thousands of symbols and is incredibly complicated. Only a very elite group of bureaucrats that kept track of all shares and inheritance contracts in a local governmental office were versed in it. And this elite also used these techniques among themselves as equals, with the earliest recorded allotment of high offices likewise being found within the Northern Mesopotamian city of Assur (Westbrook & Beckman, 2003). The head of the city house managed economical life by recording and collecting taxes, fees, and debts during the old Assyrian period (c. 2025 BC – c. 1364 BC) and was chosen by drawing lots every year and gave his name to the year he served (p.438). Objects of later periods like Yaḥalu's pūru (the Assyrian word for lot) shown on **figure 4** (p. 53) dated to the 9th century BCE represent a decision die to assign official mandates of Assur by lot (Hallo, 1983). Mandates were written in detail on 4 sides, but it remains unclear why two sides were empty as this die could also be stacked.

But assignment of duties is also seen mythologically in the myth of Atra-Hasis with the Igigi Gods, being lower-ranking Gods to the higher Anunnaki, tasked with intense labor to redirect rivers for irrigation. They cast lots among each other to determine their roles in maintaining the cosmos until they eventually rebel, leading to the creation of humankind as slaves from blood and clay. Concerning the spiritual world of the Mesopotamians, the primal Gods were indeed very anthropomorphic and represented more of a ruling class with the mythology telling how agrarian societies started to create levels of hierarchies.

The cultural technique of casting lots, no matter what object, appears to have stood the test of time, and most likely everyone back then knew what it meant. A binding contract.

We hear many familiar stories in this myth with the Gods being angry with humanity and invoking a flood to wipe them out, but Atra-Hasis was warned by the god Enki (Ea) of the coming flood and told to build a boat to save himself, his family and various animals. We of course see this story surviving as the story of Noah's ark in the Tanakh just like others: In the epic of Gilgamesh the pure hero Enkidu had been kicked out of paradise after encountering civilization like Adam and the garden of Eden, and the Gods later punished the city of Uruk with wrath of fire for its wickedness just like Sodom and Gomorrah.

These stories are found in Genesis along with the mythological travels of Abraham, dated roughly around 1500 BC between the three big centers of civilization of the time: Babylon to the East, Assyria to the north, and Egypt to the Southwest (Finkelstein & Silberman, 2001). Within this cultural melting pot, a revolutionary Hebrew writing system of Proto-Canaanite and Phoenician emerged (around 1000 BC). Consisting of only 22 phonetic symbols it was a much easier system to learn reading and writing compared to the alternatives of the time, as in thousands of symbols in cuneiform or Egyptian Hieroglyphs (Goody, 1986). The Tanakh is so relevant because it describes the transition of a nomadic and illiterate bronze age culture (who cast sacred lots) into a settled iron age culture, becoming the first widely literate people (Ong, 1982).

Within this mythological light we can see the legalities of God promising land. When the Lord had given the (written) law of the 10 commandments to Moses he had also instructed to cast lots upon arrival. In the Tanakh we read about the act of casting lots around 80 times (depending on the translation) with around 70 (the rest will be analyzed in the following pages) concerning land division when the 12 tribes arrived in the promised land of Canaan. This was done by Joshua, the most trusted general of Moses and political successor after his death. He was to conquer and divide the land, which we also find in the more census-oriented book of Numbers, serving legal documentation. This "paradox of divination" (Jackson, 2020) in the Old Testament is frequently pointed out among biblical scholars concerning the frequent use of casting lots, dubbed "cleromancy". But we know now from studying Mesopotamia that this is everything but divination, but a dry bureaucratic legal act of the ancient Near East to ratify ownership. In this sense it was indeed holy since it concerned property rights that had to be honored. This institution however had been forgotten for most part of written history.

THE DIVINE LOT

The Hebrews knew of the civilizing nature of casting lots when reading Proverbs like:

"Casting the lot settles disputes and keeps strong opponents apart." (Proverbs 18:18). Since the nation of Israel was not a homogenous group but an alliance of different tribes, the mythological instance that the brothers Moses and Aaron had taken on leadership roles instead of power being more broadly distributed among the tribes of Israel almost caused revolt led by Korah (Numbers 16:1-35). God punished the rebels and instructed Moses to collect 12 rods from each tribe's elder chiefs to resolve the dispute. After each had laid down a rod in front of the tabernacle, Aaron's rod had sprouted, legitimizing his status. A possible mythological description of sortition by lots as I would suggest, being only subject to the bias and AGENCY of God. Aaron's descendants would be known as the Levites and were granted no allotted land but would rather have to stay unbiased and manage ritual and law. Aaron's rod was placed within the ark of the covenant which had already held the 10 commandments. A primal division of church and state, or ritual and law. (Numbers 17)

But Proverbs also state a more divine nature of the practice when writing: "The lot is cast into the lap, but its every decision is from the LORD." (Proverbs 16:33). This led many scholars to the understanding of its divinity since it was closely connected to ritual and the priesthood, like God's instructions in Leviticus (16:8) for Aaron – the first priest – that he is to cast lots over two goats for a scapegoat on the day of atonement. This divine nature will be analyzed thoroughly, since in mythological Hebrew times there were three ways of communicating with God: Him speaking directly to the Israelites via 1. prophets or 2. dreams, and only one way to inquire of him, 3. the Urim. It was instructed by God on mount Sinai when Moses was receiving the law and instructions how to build the ritualistic items. The first thing was "an Ephod", a mythical and highly ritualized garment (Ex 28,6-14), into which the Urim and Thummim were to be put, the divine lots. (Lindblom, 1962)

Ritual was necessary to give society structure, but the Urim was not a way to communicate with God from the very beginning. In Genesis, during Abraham's chaotic travels, no lots were being cast to divine God's will. In the second book of Exodus out of Egyptian servitude, YHWH first only spoke directly with the prophetic Moses "face to face, as one speaks to a friend" (Exodus 33:11), who was the charismatic earthly leader of communicating law as well as military leadership to the promised land. But he did not speak to Aaron or the designated priesthood serving as a mediator in charge of ritual and divine inquiries for grand military or political decisions, like affirming leaders.

THE URIM AND THUMMIM

Inquiring Urim (אֲרִיִּם) and Thummim (תְּמִיִּם) must be seen as something different than profane casting of lots for land division, sortition or settling disputes, for which “goral” (גֹּרָל) was used, which stems from the word for “stone” or “pebble”. This was all done among equal options, even though not irrelevant. Certainly, sending thousands of men to die or not were unequal options but the truthful way of the Urim. Urim being something like “lights” and Thummim something like “perfections” suggesting a sense of truth, wholeness, or the ideal state of correctness (Kitz, 1997).

An Ephod is described as a sort of harness onto which the “breastpiece of decision” or “breastpiece of judgement” (depending on the translation) was tied over the priest’s heart (Exodus 28:15). It was to be a square, a span (about 23 centimeters) long and wide, folded double and to be “skillfully fashioned for making decisions” (Exodus 28:30). Into it the Urim and the Thummim were to be put, which most scholars have suggested to represent stones meaning Yes or No but Kitz points out that the suffix “-im” represents the plural form (Kitz, 1997). A plural form would certainly allow for more nuanced interpretations or be used like the later Greek Kleroterion²². There is no sufficient documentation how it was used, and the uses could be multiple, however we know that it always produced definite answers that did not need interpretation.

Making it a wearable garment could represent the whole nation “knit together as one man” (Judges 20:11) by the unbiased priest so that only the united nation of all tribes could inquire of God. This gives the Urim a special meaning instead of having multiple bystanders casting regular lots likely to get different results. The breast piece was said to fasten well, and the garments had to be made sturdy to prevent tearing and the garment also featured bells. The prevention of tearing and bells suggest an intention of movement. The fundamental idea seems to be providing a mechanism of maximum randomness with minimal manipulation to generate unbiased but clearly visible results to everyone present, regardless of literacy and language or dialect. If we think about the importance of an impartial decision maker, which is the duty of the priesthood, then the pressure on his fairness must have been immense, since honoring the outcome was a divine duty of communal responsibility.

²² See page 84.

We learn some insights on its communal function when Joshua is made the successor of Moses that the whole community was to be present, while the priest would stand before him to obtain decisions for him by inquiring of the Urim before the Lord if Joshua was approved. We see the Urim in action when assigning military campaigns or deciding whether to fight or cease. Since the land of Canaan had many other inhabitant tribes to be subjugated, these military missions were assigned to tribes by lot and they often cooperated to be stronger together: “And Judah said unto Simeon his brother, come up with me into my lot, that we may fight against the Canaanites; and I likewise will go with thee into thy lot.” (Judges 1:3)

The Urim and Thummim were certainly put to test after Joshua’s death, with the twelve tribes lacking centralized leadership in the times of Judges and the priesthood losing trust. “In those days, Israel had no king; everyone did as they saw fit” (Judges 17:6, 18:1, 19:1, 21:25). A priestly Levite had a concubine who left him, but when he passed with her through Gibeah of the tribe of Benjamin, she got raped to death, which caused tremendous outrage among all other tribes demanding justice. However, the house of Benjamin refused and prepared for war instead: Now the remaining 11 tribes of the house of Israel remained “knit together as one man” chose to fight the tribe in their city of Gibeah and declared “we will go up against it by lot” (Judges 20:28). They went up to Beth-el (where the ark was during these days) to inquire of God who shall go up to battle. The tribe of Judah was chosen but lost (22.000 men) (Judges 20:23). They wept all night and inquired a second time if they should battle again, which was again confirmed and this time the tribe of Israel was chosen, with it again losing (18.000 men). Again, they wept but inquired a third time if they should continue the battle or cease. Israel had to go another time, but this time developed a strategy to lure the tribes of Benjamin out of the city to then take over the city and finally destroy the warriors of Benjamin (25.000 men) (Judges 20:27–28). The battle had finally been won, but they wept again since the house of Benjamin had now been cut from the common nation. When during the next assembly the tribe of Jabesh-Gilead did not take part, it then suffered the immediate consequence of being (almost) completely destroyed by the remaining community of 10 immediately banding together without casting lots. The SACRED EARNEST to uphold the common institutional mechanism had begun to fall apart.

About real divinatory uses of casting lots in the Tanakh, Westbrook and Beckman claim oracular procedures for legal purposes like litigation of a perpetrator are only to be attested for certain in Egypt and Israel, with only the latter also used casting lots for this purpose. (Westbrook, Beckman p.35). But like Mesopotamian legal practices, Mosaic law typically relied on oaths, court rulings and evidence and the only instances when superstitiously casting lots for litigation had only been done by people who deviated from the supposed will of God. Saul mimicked a filtering process that God himself had done to find a perpetrator, using lots to identify his son Jonathan as having eaten honey against his orders, but Saul had already fallen from God's grace. (1 Samuel 14:36-45) And in the famous story of Jonah, who was part of a crew of sailors getting caught in a storm, they draw lots to determine who was upsetting God. Jonah drew the short end of the stick, admitted to his sins, and was cast off the boat saving the others. He was later swallowed by a big fish where he repented for three days and ultimately survived (Jonah 1, 2). But Jonah's personal journey is also biblically unique in his reluctance to obey God's command yet being at his mercy. We can therefore correctly file these unique instances within the Old Testament under cleromancy as in acts of superstition. I therefore argue that divination using lots is generally an offshoot of a practical technique that had gained great communal acceptance as a consultative institution.

FROM RITUAL TO SCRIPTURE

After the destruction of the first temple of Jerusalem in 586 BC the priesthood ceased to be along with the Urim. During the relatively brief period within Babylonian exile the Rabbinic class of scribes took over spiritual leadership of communities in the diaspora and taught in the new Synagogues. Literacy now spread to a large part within the Hebrew population since kids were taught from a young age to preserve its culture and history. Trust in scripture established a new common source of SACRED EARNEST within a holy book.

During the Babylonian exile we get records of views of casting lots for divinatory purposes among many different methods of divination throughout the ancient Near East. „For the king of Babylon (comment: Nebuchadnezzar II) will stop at the fork in the road, at the junction of the two roads, to seek an omen: He will cast lots with arrows, he will consult his idols, he will examine the liver.“ (Ezekiel 21:21). Here we not only see that arrows were used as lots but that the use of casting lots was now clearly associated with any other divination method

and that the inability to make simple decisions, clearly depicted by a fork in the road, was not something a king was honored for. The views on a divine lot must have changed significantly within the Hebrew realm.

When the reconstruction of the second temple started in 537 BCE, the priesthood and its rituals were to be reestablished when “The governor ordered them not to eat any of the most sacred food until there was a priest ministering with the Urim and Thummim.” (Ezra 2:63). But it is not apparent that the Ephod and Urim have been reintroduced after the second temple's completion. However, the casting of regular lots (“goral” גורל) was still done to assign priestly duties (1 Chronicles 24:5, 31) and the duties of the temple musicians (1 Chronicles 25:8:). In the book of Nehemiah, which documents the restoration of the religious and social order among the returned exiles, lots were cast to determine which families would supply wood for the altar (Nehemiah 10:34) and which families would live in Jerusalem (Nehemiah 11:1). But it would be a change from divine lots as an institution towards divine scripture as an institution. The later parts of the Tanakh are also more historic records with Malachi being considered the last prophet, though only a minor one, during the Persian period (c. 450–420 BCE). According to Rabbinic tradition prophecy through men or dreams had later ceased to exist. Jews now turned to the law of the Torah as the primary source of divine guidance and the Rabbinic scribes took on a greater role in interpreting God’s will (Neusner, 1987).

But the magic surrounding lots has lived on in the heads and traditions of Judaism with the Purim fest being celebrated to this day, with “Purim” being the Persian word for lots. Coming from the book of Esther, which is sometimes referred to as one of the “Four strange books of the bible” attributed to being more inclined to romanticism and storytelling. Haman, the advisor of Xerxes, had cast lots to decide on a date when to exterminate all Jews. Esther, the second wife of Xerxes, had been Jewish though, but had always been advised to conceal her origin by her cousin and guardian, Mordecai. Upon gaining knowledge of Haman’s plot Esther revealed her true identity to the king who had Haman hanged instead of Mordecai and issued a decree that allowed the Jews to defend themselves leading to their victory over their enemies against all odds.

GREEK RECORDS AMONG OTHER CULTURES OF THE TIME

We know much more about the world of thought among the Greeks since they had moved from illiteracy to literacy without having to develop their own writing system from scratch. Instead, they adapted the phonetic writing systems of the Levante while inventing symbols for vowels (Goody, 1986). At the time of Herodotus' *Histories*, written in the 5th century BCE, we find the casting of lots among many cultures of the ancient Near East for very grand decisions among the Persians, Scythians and Greeks.

He tells of the Lydians (who had invented coins) that they invented all other forms of games and how they would play all day to forget the troubles of hunger. From previously mentioned archeological evidence we learn that the area of Anatolia was an early breeding ground of games and toys, from ball to knucklebones and dice. But regarding dice the Lydians themselves claim not to have invented them, and we know them to have originated further East in India (see page 65). King Croesus of the Lydians divided his own people into two groups, and had it decided by lot who would attack Persia (1.94) (perhaps a coin toss).

The six successors of Cambyses II had to decide how to continue the rule of empire, "whether we make the choice by casting lots for the prize, or by letting the people decide which of us they will have to rule over them". In the end they engage in a horse race to claim who will become ruler, won by Darius I. (3.83-84). So, the democratic option of voting was known, just like casting lots (ALEA) appears to be a valued tradition among equals, but in the end a merit-based way (AGÔN) of who is the fittest was chosen. Darius' successor King Xerxes I. would be in the book of Esther and the Purim fest (see page 82).

It is different from the accounts given about the Scythians, nomadic and brutal riders of the Eurasian steppe, like the later Huns or Mongols. By releasing a bundle of willow sticks on the ground and then sorting the rods one by one in some ritualistic process which is repeated three times. (4.67-68) It may also be the interpretation of a random pattern of scattering them on the ground, but the sorting can also suggest some kind of quantifiable outcome, that might bear resemblance to the I Ching and the Scythians indeed came from the East. It might indeed be more of an elaborate divination method.

And in Athens when the council of the confederation of city states was divided to go to war or not; A tiebreaker vote fell on the polemarch, the highest general, chosen by lot among the archons of the city states who also all chosen by lot. The battle-order, which regiment was to go, also appears to be determined by lot. (6, 109-111) So, representatives or regiments were chosen by lot among equals. But grand decisions were done by vote.

These are four very different uses and outcomes of lots that should not be all put in one basket. Croesus is clearly highlighted by his arrogance and seeing even the most relevant decisions as irrelevant, in the end losing it all. Athens had a sophisticated clarity how lots were to be used and how not to be used. The Persians were generally aware and open to many different approaches. And the nomadic Scythians used it as some more ritualistic practice among a great communitas. This shows why using a fine brush provides clarity that casting lots was not simply “a practice” or “divination” but a cultural technique applicable for many uses.

In the *Politics in the ancient world* (Finley, 1983) the secular and institutional uses of lots are well described. Early Athens had the Cleruchy (κληρουχία) system, however not primarily for the purpose of land division but for assignment by lot. A Cleruch had legal ownership of a lot of land – called “kleros” (κλήρος) – assigned by the state after it had been conquered. The Athenian Cleruchy system is dated to the 6th century BCE in Salamis, an Attic Island near Athens, as well as Sigeion, near the ancient city of Troy, where Athenian settlers under Phrynon, a winner of the Olympic games, arrived around 600 BCE. With the restoration of the Athenian Democracy in 403 BC most state offices and court juries were selected among the citizens of the Athenian polis through the Kleroterion (κληρωτήριο), a lot-machine into which black or white pebbles were put, representing Yes or No. The number was flexible according to the number of mandates that had to be assigned, and the random results would then be placed on the names of possible candidates to be taken or not.

THE DEIFICATION OF CHANCE

Along with the use of lots, the Greeks have adopted parts of its mythology from the ancient Near East. In *The Iliad* (Homer, c. 800 BCE/1996) we find the Mesopotamian story of the three main Gods casting lots to divide the universe alive 1000 years later, when Poseidon speaks:

“And in three-fold wise are all things divided, and unto each hath been apportioned his own domain. I verily, when the lots were shaken, won for my portion the gray sea to be my habitation forever, and Hades won the murky darkness, while Zeus won the broad heaven amid the air and the clouds; but the earth and high Olympus remain yet common to us all.” [190-191]

Now it is Zeus getting the heavens, Poseidon the sea, and Hades the underworld. Also, the idea of Olymp as a common, neutral place like Jerusalem, shows the Hebrew influence. But if the primal Gods were not in control of chance or fate, then who was? Greek mythology would bear the Moirai, the three goddesses of fate spinning the thread from past, present and future.²³ They were daughters of Zeus but also more omnipotent than their father. Their mother is Themis (justice) but also Nyx (the night) according to the *Theogony* (Hesiod, ca. 750–650 BCE/2006, ll. 217–222, 901–906). So, we can ascribe something hidden to them while they are mostly described as fair and without bias. As written by Pindar they uphold the divine order as well as helping Heracles in establishing the Olympic Games (Pindar, c. 470 BCE/1990), which is dated to 776 BCE. In the *Republic* (Plato c. 380 BCE/2004) Socrates explains how souls are presented all kinds of life forms, human and animal, in the form of lots by the first of the Moirai, Lachesis, who is literally the “disposer of lots” from λαγχάνω *lanchánō*, “to obtain by lot, by fate, or by the will of the Gods”. They pick one which is then brought before her. The daimon (the inner voice) then leads the soul to Clotho, the second, turning her spindle to ratify the destiny until ultimately leading to Atropos, the irreversible.

A true Goddess of fortune and chance, Tyche, only became prominent during the classical Hellenistic period as mentioned by Pindar (c. 470/1990), but particularly following the conquests of Alexander and its great societal changes. Quite a different perception than a thread being spun from beginning to end, she embodies the unpredictable turns of fate influencing success and destiny able to bring forth great heroes. Her Roman equivalent, Fortuna, would become a deity of immense power. Fortuna, the goddess of luck, was originally depicted with a wheel, originally prayed to by seafarers for safe passage.

²³ This is also found within Nordic mythology of the three Norns (Davidson, 1988, p. 136).

FORTUNA

Fortuna would already be popular throughout the beginning of the Roman kingdom (around 550 BC) with the sixth king, Servius Tullius, carrying a legacy of being born to a slave mother but having risen to power by the blessing of Fortuna. He had 26 temples built for her and she would play a big part in Roman religion. Fortuna was praised as everyone could have the potential of rising to wealth and status. At her temples lots were cast for divination, which were called “Sortes” as in sortition. (Buchholz, 2013) (Reeves, 2015)

The temple of Fortuna Primigenia at Præneste as shown in **Figure 10** (p. 55) is close to the city of Rome, of gigantic proportions, and one of the most important oracle sites in ancient Rome. The Praeneste Fibula was also discovered in a tomb there, which could represent one of the earliest known examples of Latin writing (Hartman, 2005), linking the city to early Latin literacy and cultural development. Cicero tells how the use of sortes had gone widely out of use at his time, but described the origins of the lot oracle there, when a Prenestine noble, Numerius Suffustius, was told in a dream to split a large rock, which revealed the wooden sortes carved with ancient writing. He then cut down an olive tree dripping with honey to make an ark to store the sortes (Cicero, 1923, p.469). The sortes were made from either bronze or wood and placed within a *sittella*, an urn shaped vessel. An idea was explored of being filled with water, so that wooden lots would rise to pass through the neck to reach the top. (Buchholz, 2013) The lot was then picked by a young boy who would bring it to the altar for reading. All this points to a carefully developed mechanism to provide the least amount of human manipulation. The lots were not touched, but only the whole vessel was shaken. The decision was also not done by hand but by rising to the top, and even the person to pick it up had to be of innocent youth to show no bias would present the decision. If we must speculate how the Hebrew Ephod could have functioned as a device to produce unbiased decisions, its idea might be similar to the temple of Fortuna appearing to have been designed with high Earnest of removing the possibilities of manipulation.

Fortuna was prayed to both as a private God (*Fortuna privata*) as well as a God of the state (*Fortuna Populi Romani*) and as such she would be celebrated on June 24th, the summer solstice as we know from Ovid writing about festivities in his *Fasti* (Ovid, c. 8 CE/2000). He emphasizes the goddess's connection to the random and unpredictable aspects of life, invoked in times of need or when fate is uncertain, indicating that she can change a person's

life like flipping their fate like a coin from fortune to misfortune or vice versa, and he reminds readers that no matter how powerful a person becomes, even emperors, all remain at the mercy of Fortuna.²⁴

"Alea iacta est" meaning "The die is cast" is attributed to Julius Caesar as he crossed the Rubicon in 49 BCE (Suetonius, c. 121 CE/2001) signaling the start of civil war. Interestingly though, Roman dice were made of all shapes with only a negligible amount representing cubes. Also, the placement of pips on so many differently found dice followed no specific order. None of this was due to a lack of craftsmanship, which the Romans most certainly possessed. Romans called astragals, Tali, but they mostly had the numbers 1, 2, 3, and 6 assigned (Bell, 1960), compared to the Greek standard of 1, 3, 4, 6. (Schädler, 1996), making lower numbers more likely than a unique high number of 6. Most scholars attribute it to their spiritual world as seeing the outcome of dice throws as expressions of divine will or fate. Certainly, the cult of Fortuna gave them a greater obsession with randomness. Perhaps Romans thought it more fun when someone brought a new uniquely shaped die and cubic dice or even distributions of numbers were seen as boring in their ability to provide a fair distribution of outcomes. Roman soldiers as well as a general code of honor showed their status by how little they cared about outcomes. Making the decision to cast dice means, taking fate into one's own hands but letting Fortuna decide the outcome.

Gambling and games of chance are widely documented among all classes of Rome. Accounts include leaders like Mark Anton, notorious cheater Caligula, Claudius, Nero, and Commodus, who had built special dicing rooms in his palace. However, gambling was officially not seen as virtuous and gambling laws had already existed since the republic in 204 BC with the *Lex Alearia* prohibiting games of chance that involved betting money while the *Lex Cornelia de Aleatoribus* (81 BCE) legitimized only bets tied to activities perceived as virtuous like athletic contests (AGÔN). However, there were exceptions for specific events during the Saturnalia festival where many impulsive activities were celebrated (Smith, 1875). But gambling laws were only loosely enforced and the fact that Roman society was charged with superstition and its praise of bread and games did not curb its success.

²⁴ Rome issued a coin in 69 BCE showing the box marked "SORS" for the lots and an image of the goddess Fortuna on the other side. See **Figure 9** (p. 56).

CICERO ON LOTS AND CHANCE

Contrary to widespread dicing and gambling it has been seen within elite circles as morally depraved, being frequently classed with adulterers, drunks and mimes. Cicero certainly saw it this way along with his disdain for superstition which he brought forth in *De Divinatione* during his exile. Here he puts up an argument with Stoics, represented by his brother Quintus, who defended divination as part of philosophy as a connection with nature and the divine in a deterministic world view. Cicero defends the nature of chance, as in the original sense of accident: “Hence it seems to me that it is not in the power even of God himself to know what event is going to happen accidentally and by chance.” (Book II, p. 391)

Asking about the nature of lots he writes:

” It is much like playing at morra²⁵, dice, or knucklebones, in which recklessness and luck prevail rather than reflection and judgement. The whole scheme of divination by lots was fraudulently contrived from mercenary motives, or as a means of encouraging superstition and error. “ (p.469)

Quintus also asks how it could be anything other than the Gods if one rolled 100 Venus throws in succession, something so unlikely that Cicero uses it to demonstrate the level of superstition and to destroy his argument with rationality: “Nothing is so uncertain as a cast of the dice ... Then are we, like fools, to prefer to say that it happened by the direction of Venus rather than by chance?” (p.509)

The philosopher marked a break in calling out an absurdity of attributing divine will to lot-casting and chance in general, advocating for reason to reach conclusions. While neglecting his skepticism of the divine, many people who would later be Christians would share his criticism of superstitious Roman customs, but not for the sake of rationalism but for distancing themselves from pagan practices, they would label as divination.

²⁵ Old Roman hand game. See p. 62

HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF EARLY CHRISTIANITY

In Christianity Jewish, Greek and Roman influence merge within the power of scripture. A "Messiah" (*mashiach*) originally referred to Jewish kings like Saul, David, and Solomon, and it was the Jewish hope at that time to restore a monarchy and the independence of its people after being under the rule of many different empires for centuries since the destruction of the first Temple (Ben-Sasson, 1976). Jesus of Nazareth spoke against Roman occupation but also diverted from Mosaic Law not preaching political revolt but a kingdom "not of this world" (John 18:36). After his crucifixion, Paul, originally a devout defender of Judaism, became the first convert and would start to preach throughout the Roman Empire to Jews and Gentiles (non-Jews) alike to be included into God's covenant. It is the most notable difference to Judaism which remained exclusive in keeping its cultural traditions alive. A deterministic concept of God was influenced by Stoic and Platonic philosophy as seen when Paul preached in the Areopagus in Athens that God had "marked out their allotted times²⁶ (emphasis by author) in history and the boundaries of their lands." (Acts 17:26). Jesus would now also be called the Greek word for Messiah, Christos.

After the temple was destroyed in 70 CE a second time, Jewish Messianic movements peaked, and Rome met unexpected resistance from Bar Kokhba's messianic revolt (132 CE). It infuriated emperor Hadrian to devastate Judea, renaming it Syria Palaestina, and Jerusalem into Aelia Capitolina which Jews were now forbidden to enter (Lewin, 2005). Many Jews now turned to Christianity which had completely redefined messianism from an earthly Israel to a heavenly kingdom with divine salvation in the afterlife (which Judaism was not concerned with). The story of Jesus resonated with many marginalized groups of the empire, familiar with crucifixion and oppression. But even though Paul diverted from Judaism he interpreted its scriptures in the light of Jesus' teaching, most likely to try to persuade other Jews who had little left except for their scriptures and now spread across the empire (Hays, 1989). So even though Christianity diverted from Judaism it still relied on the Hebrew Tanakh for divine legitimacy. The Christian bible therefore consists of it (already translated into Greek in the 3rd century BCE) as the Old Testament and a new interpretative appendix, the New Testament, which argues in many letters among its early followers that the life of Jesus, the Christ, had already been revealed by a prophetic God's plan through scripture.

²⁶ compare with Socrates' description of Lachesis. See p. 85

THE CHRIST ABOVE THE LOT

The main theme that started the research of this thesis concerns the Roman soldiers casting lots about the garments of Jesus while being on the cross showed to be one of the instances that made early Christians believe that chance could not possibly exist. It covers 4 of the 5 mentions of the word “lot” in the New Testament since the scene is mentioned by all 4 Evangelists in the gospels (emphases added by author):

”When they had crucified [Jesus], they divided up his clothes by casting lots. This happened that the scripture might be fulfilled which said, 'They divided my garments among them and cast lots for my clothing’ (Matthew 27:25)

"Dividing up his clothes, they cast lots to see what each would get" (Mark 15:24b)

"And they divided up his clothes by casting lots" (Luke 23:34b)

“Let’s not tear it,” they said to one another. “Let’s decide by lot who will get it.”
(John 19:24)

What Matthew meant by “this happened that the scripture might be fulfilled” is clarified by both Matthew and Mark, who included this famous opening sentence as Christ’s only statement while upon the cross (Matt. 27:46; Mark 15:34):

“My God, my God, why hast thou forsaken me?” (emphasis added by author)

The mentioned fulfillment of scripture references the psalm of king David (Psalm 22,1) within the Old Testament, which had been written about 1000 years earlier:

“My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?” (emphasis added by author)

(. . .)

They pierce my hands and my feet.

All my bones are on display; people stare and gloat over me.

They divide my clothes among them and cast lots for my garment.” (Psalms 22, 16-18)

1000 years after the original Psalm was written it was now interpreted to be a prophesied image of Jesus' crucifixion and the division of his garments by lot. The reference serves to legitimize Jesus Christ as the true Messiah, coming from the house of David. It was especially Matthew who saw numerous prophecies in scripture being fulfilled, like in

(Matthew 2:13-15) he claims Jesus' flight to Egypt fulfilled in (Hosea 11:1) "Out of Egypt I called my son". But Hosea had referred to Israel's exodus, not a future Messiah. The famous virgin birth (Matthew 1:22-23) was supposedly prophesied in (Isaiah 7:14) "The virgin will conceive and give birth to a son". Being born in Bethlehem (Matthew 2:1-6) pointed to (Micah 5:2) "Out of you, Bethlehem ... will come a ruler". Entering Jerusalem on a donkey (Matthew 21:1-11.) pointed to (Zechariah 9:9) "See, your king comes to you, righteous and victorious, lowly and riding on a donkey."

It was in essence bibliomancy, since all these references point to randomly different times in history, places and narratological contexts in the original Jewish Tanakh. The basis of Christian belief is the fulfillment of prophecy as a divine plan predetermined by God, revealed through scripture. Its early believers were trying to reveal hidden knowledge and truth by picking in old texts as if it was a liver. These new literate mantises were learned in scripture but would not imagine to someday evolve into a movement with any earthly power, let alone leading the Roman empire. That the original Jewish Tanakh would become the foundation of thought and faith of Christianity and Islam, a millennia after its writing, can only be beyond the wildest imagination of its original authors. Amounting to approximately 4,5 billion people today, these would grow into the two largest religions on earth.

The original Exegesis, scriptural interpretation, is known as typology and was foundational to early Christian theology. It was pattern recognition of Types in the Old Testament with Antitypes of the growing New Testament (Barrett, 2004). By writing letters to one another about a joyful, dopamine-emitting, experience of random pattern recognition, it must have been quite a playful activity among displaced and persecuted people who projected all their wishes onto reading their holy scripture. Most became more allegorical types and the amount of believed revelations varies among biblical scholars. Some Christian groups continue this form of Exegesis until modern times with J. Barton Payne identifying 574 verses of alleged fulfilled prophecies (Payne, 1973, p. 678). What makes the Roman scene of casting lots for his garments so special though is that it is one of the few instances that was supposedly recorded by all four Evangelicals at the time of the crucifixion while also referencing a psalm of king David, the perfect role model of a Jewish Messiah. The actual casting of lots of Roman soldiers had nothing to do with any moral view about gambling or playing dice but was simply a unique puzzle piece of connecting stories A scene, so strongly believed to be impossible to have been by chance.

FROM KLEROS TO CLERICS

The only other mention of casting lots in the New Testament is when the apostles' cast lots for a replacement of Judas Iscariot after his suicide while praying: "Lord ... show us what of these two [candidates] you have chosen (emphasis by author)." (Acts 1:21-26, NIV). The practice of sortition by lot had therefore been alive around the time of Jesus - whether profanely or to consult God's will. But the Apostolic Church would later condemn sortilege as a relic of paganism until emperor Justinian had ultimately banned the custom to elect officials and priests via sortition in the 6th century. But by this time the Greek word for lot, κλήρος, had long undergone a remarkable change into a class of priests, chosen by God.

St. Cyprian of Carthage (c. 200–258 CE) already makes a distinction of members of the ministry and ordinary people in his letters, starting with: "Clero et plebi universae" – "To the clergy and all the people" (1886, Epistula 1.1) and describes how they were divinely appointed "*Clerus divina ordinatione institutus*" – "The clergy, established by divine ordination" (Epistula 67.2). He also explains the church hierarchy of bishops (episcopus) who are considered successors of the apostles and shepherds of the whole church. They can ordain the broader clergy (clerus) in assisting the bishop without having his full authority. Eusebius of Caesarea (c. 260–339 CE) refers to "Bishops and clergy" which reflects how the word κλήρος has changed from being an object of choosing to divinely chosen people.

Within the 4th century the Christian church went from being persecuted to being tolerated in 313 CE. It became the official religion of the Roman empire by 380 CE outlawing paganism. St. Jerome, living during this period, translated the Bible into Latin with his interpretations seeking to differentiate Christianity from pagan customs. In his interpretation of Numbers (Jerome, 1994), he critiqued the use of sticks or rods for divination, which would strike the very core of the early priesthood of Aaron (see p. 78), had he not highlighted instead how his rod was a divine instrument demonstrating God's authority, as seen in its blossoming (Numbers 17). But he based his critique on the critique he found in Hosea 4:12 of the Old Testament, where the prophet refers to Israel's idolatry and unfaithfulness to God by stating: "My people consult a wooden idol, and a diviner's staff speaks to them. A spirit of prostitution leads them astray; they are unfaithful to their God." (Hosea 4:12, NIV) St. Jerome attributed this to ancient Greek practices of drawing lots, which now became something misleading instead of coming from the Lord.

SORTES BIBLICAE – NEW CHANCES WITHIN A CODEX

Randomly picking a passage within ancient Jewish, Greek and Roman scripture was a contemporary divinatory custom among many literate people of the time (Gamble, 1995, p. 240). But since early Christians deeply believed in hidden revelations and prophecies within scripture, the “Sortes Biblicae” represented more than spiritual guidance through the day. In *Ecclesiastical History* (Book VI, Ch. 3 & 4) Eusebius of Caesarea mentions how Origen and other early Christians would pick passages from Psalms or Prophets at random to interpret them as typological references to Christ’s ministry or contemporary events.

Around the 1st and 2nd century AD literary cross-referencing would become much easier as Christians were among the first groups to widely adopt the new Roman “Codex” format (Hurtado, 2006, p. 43) of organizing text. Individual pages were now bound together and sandwiched between two hard protective covers. Since then, humans would start “flipping” or “turning” pages of a bound book instead of having to use a scroll, while “picking” pages at random was also made possible with this new (lottery) format. (Roberts & Skeat, 1983).

St. Augustine describes opening the Bible at random on Romans 13:13-14 leading to his conversion by seeing his personal story mirroring Paul’s. He wrote this in his *Confessions* (Book VIII, Ch. 12, p.152) shortly after he became Bishop of Hippo in 396 CE and after the 27 books of the New Testament were officially canonized during the Councils in Hippo in 393 AD and Carthage in 397 AD. Like many other clerics however, St. Augustine himself did not like this divinatory use and the Council of Vannes (465 CE) finally condemned the use of Sortes Biblicae as improper use of sacred scripture and superstitious divination, which was reinforced by the Council of Agde (506 CE) and Council of Orléans (511 CE). This was not a light matter since these councils aimed to ensure that scriptural interpretation (Exegesis) remained within church control and individual interpretations were now prohibited as divinatory practices (Hefele, 1985).

From casting lots to sortition or opening a book at random, many playful practices of randomization assisted the creation of Christianity but were ultimately banned to safeguard the power of a theological elite by applying the label of divination.

THE DEATH OF RANDOMNESS

Nothing happens by chance is proclaimed by St. Augustine of Hippo as he approaches the philosophical issue between randomness and divine providence (Reeves, 2015) in the *The City of God* (c. 426 BCE/2009) and Christianity was now to win the argument against Roman paganism.

Augustine mockingly praises Fortuna as certainly being among the most powerful Gods, by saying that “[Fortuna] certainly ought to occupy a pre-eminent place among the select gods, since she has such a preeminent power over them.” (City of God, VII, p.3). But he also tries to highlight the absurdities of praying to her by asking: “And why is she worshipped, when she is so blind that she runs up against anyone whatever at random, and clings even to those who despise her?” (City of God, IV, p.18) portraying her like a slanderous woman instead to make the push of her high pedestal even more dramatic. The philosophical battle with Fortuna is a profound one, and in Augustine’s explanation about “the tunic without seam” concerning the division of Jesus garments, he mentions that the Christian faith “is given by God’s hidden grace as by lot” making striking parallels towards Fortuna, but writing that

“God (...) himself gives earthly kingdoms to both good men and bad. He does not do this rashly, or as it were at random, for he is God, not Fortune. Rather he acts in accordance with an order of things and times which is hidden from us, but entirely known to him.” (p.33)

Rhetorically speaking a chaotic woman was now replaced by a man with a plan as he writes “And truly, if Fortuna speaks, she should at least speak, not with a womanly, but with a manly voice” (p.156) and philosophically speaking, Randomness with Determinism.

At this point I propose to question if the ability to believe in an almighty God with a divine plan being entirely hidden but ultimately fair, was even possible without the cultivation of trust in the justice of lots millennia beforehand. We had cultivated to outsource our AGENCY into the trust of the lot and to accept its outcome without question because the community depended on upholding this SACRED EARNEST. The grand hypothesis here being that the idea of God as an object of thought has stemmed from the use of objects as lots.

Once this idea had established its power, the original form was no longer necessary, but to the contrary, a threat. Just like the priestly Urim were replaced by the Rabbinic scribes, Fortuna was replaced with the Holy Bible and its clergy, however on a much bigger scale.

Since Christians rely on the bible as a holy book while also dismissing casting lots as a pagan practice, Christian eschatology was in a bind to make sense how to outlaw something that God had specifically instructed his people to do in the Old Testament (Reeves, 2015, p.10). Casting lots had therefore remained a fragile topic, stemming from the instance that since it had been called “cleromancy” by John of Damascus²⁷ its original institutional legal practice had been forgotten. That this had remained an issue within the church almost a Millenia after Augustine can be exemplified with Thomas of Aquinas addressing the issue within his *Summa Theologiae* by carefully dividing it into three categories (p.11): First, casting lots for settling disputes and for division when two parties can’t agree is allowed but only as a rare exception.²⁸ Second, casting lots for divination was always wrong. The third category however is not concerning play, which does not even appear to be on the radar of a possible use case but being “consultative” lots of God. How this is to be considered different from divination is quite hard to tell, but to inquire God’s will was now considered to be only used in extreme cases because a devout Christian and the church was guided by the Holy Spirit and uses prayer and scripture to self-reflect and find guidance. Ultimately its clergy was now the authority of interpreting scripture, while the lot remained of the utmost sanctity.

Christianity had declared war against randomness by distancing itself from paganism both philosophically in its turn against Fortuna and practically by banning casting lots almost entirely. Even E.B. Tylor mentions the rare treatise *Of the nature of using lots*. (1619) by puritan Thomas Gataker on how „the light use of it [lots] therefore to be an abuse of God’s name“ (Gataker, 1619; Tylor, 1871, chapter iii). The theory of probability during those times must have come as a revolution of thought in direct contrast to the church, not morally in opposition to gambling but philosophically in opposition to determinism and divine providence. After being the dominant ideology influencing Europe for over a millennia most European thinkers must have perceived the interconnection of chance with the divine as common to the mind of ancient people, since as far as they could read within their own ancient literature, this appeared to be the case. The medieval theological perspective on using dice in board games can thus be best summed up by D.R. Bellhouse when interpreting Calvinist Lambert Daneau: “to use randomizers for trifling matters such as gaming is to profane the majesty and power of God” (Bellhouse, 1988, p. 68)

²⁷ *Exposition of the Orthodox Faith* (c. 733 CE). See chapter A.3. Divination in this thesis on p.33

²⁸ Apparently even Justinian allowed such a loophole.

ISLAM AGAINST AZLAM

The Qur'an steps in line with the belief in one God only, and the Christian way of seeing holy scripture revealed through prophecy and the reward for the righteous on the Day of Judgement. Worldly life is not merely considered a test for the afterlife but is described four times as play (Sura 6:32, 29:64, 47:36, 57:20): "This worldly life is no more than play and amusement. But the Hereafter is indeed the real life, if only they knew." (29:64).

The Surahs of Al-Ma'idah (5:3 and 5:90) prominently concern themselves with gambling and casting lots according to most English translations. However, it is more specifically divination arrows (Azlām, الأزلام), used as lots, that are forbidden:

"O you who have believed, indeed, intoxicants, gambling, [sacrificing on] stone alters [to other than Allah], and divining arrows are but defilement from the work of Satan, so avoid it that you may be successful." (5:90, Sahih International)

The Qu'ran is the only Abrahamic holy book to mention gambling as „Maisir“ (مَيْسِر) which is associated with acquiring something without labor. However, it represented a generally discussed topic of the Abrahamic literal world at the time and place. The Talmud shaped Jewish thought and law (Halakha) for centuries on topics of ethics and religious practices and consists of Rabbinic debates (Gemara) and legal rulings on the Torah (Mishnah). The Jerusalem Talmud, compiled in the 3rd–4th century CE did not yet mention gambling, only the later and eventually more important Babylonian Talmud²⁹, which was compiled in the 5th–6th century CE in modern day Iraq. In *Sanhedrin 24b* a specific word for dice (*b'kubiya*), derived from “cube”, first appears in Hebrew where it is debated whether people playing with dice for money³⁰ or lending money for interest are disqualified from giving testimony in court, since acquiring something without labor was deemed immoral. The discussion revolves on whether gambling is forbidden theft or a permissible pastime. The first position is held by Rami bar Chama arguing that one loses money unwillingly due to a mistaken expectation of winning, while Rav Sheishet maintains that a gambler knowingly accepts the risk. The allowed use of the regular casting of lots, “goral” (גורל), on Shabbat is also discussed in *Shabbat 149b*. It was only to be done among equal portions within one's own family, while priests could only do so for the sacrifices but not for distributive lotteries.

²⁹ Talmudic translations have been retrieved on January 23rd, 2025, from <https://www.sefaria.org/>

³⁰ The difference of games of chance vs. gambling has been discussed on page 18.

Islamic law (Sharia) is based on the jurisprudence (fiqh) of Islamic scholars by mainly two sources: The Qur'an as the divine revelation of the prophet; as well as the Sunna, accounts by witnesses of his life (the Hadiths), similar to the Evangelicals of the New Testament.

Halal – permitted – is the fair use of lots named Qur'ah (قرعة). However, it is generally discouraged since Islamic principles emphasize justice, reason and fairness through consultation and evidence. Surah (37:141-142) recounts the story of Jonah being thrown overboard after lots were drawn (فَسَاهَمَ) to show his guilt, which he repented with prayers while being inside the great fish. In Sura (3:44) Jewish priests cast lots or literally “pens” (اَهَمَ) among each other to decide who would take care of Maryam (Mary, the mother of Jesus) - something that had not been written in the bible – so it became a valid method for assigning orphans. But as casting lots seemed to have been a widespread practice among the people of Muhammed and himself (Hadith 615, 2114, 6237) it was approved for resolving disputes in matters of equal entitlement or marriage disputes like deciding which wife a husband would spend time with or selecting who will accompany one, like Muhammad did in Hadith 2593 and 2770. But in general Muhammad declared: “The drawing of lots is only for matters where there is no other way to decide.” (Hadith 2930)

Haram – prohibited – is the use of any form of lot-casting associated with gambling as in Maisir (مَيْسِر), but most importantly concerning religious matters as the prophet said: “There is no drawing of lots for religious matters.” (Hadith 2930). But even more specifically Azlām (الأزلام) of which Muhammed said: “He who draws lots (الأزلام) is not from us. It is from the work of Shaytan.” (Hadith 1598) It was divination in the Abrahamic sense to distinguish one's people from others and their cultural institutions, because Azlām (الأزلام) were the divining arrows that the Quraysh and other Arab tribes in pre-Islamic times used inside the Ka'bah, which Muhammed sought to unite under monotheism.

In the history of Prophets and Kings, *Tarikh al-Rusul wa'l-Muluk*, Al-Tabari (d. 923 CE) wrote that these arrows were consulted for important matters such as war, assigning orphans and other family and marriage disputes. In his biography of the prophet, *Sirat Rasul Allah*, Ibn Hisham (d. 833 CE) described the practice inside the Ka'bah, under the idol Hubal: “The divining arrows were ten; on seven of them was written ‘Do it’ and on three was written ‘Do not do it’ When they wanted to decide on a matter, they would cast them.” Ibn Hisham (2002). (The process has also been described in more detail on page 43).

We can see that the practice of ritually shaking arrows in a quiver was typical in the pagan Ka‘bah which saw a major religious transformation under Islam, separating itself again from pagan ritual. Representing a typical mindset of not giving up AGENCY to chance but resting it within the faith of God, Zayd ibn Amr ibn Nufayl, a ḥanīf (a pre-Islamic monotheist) stood against the prevalent practices and is attributed to saying “I determine my fate with my own hand, not with the *Azlam*. If it is right, then so be it; if it deviates, then so be it.”

The Arabic word for arrow is “Sahm” (سَهْم) and also has familiar meanings related to lots as in “share”, “portion”, or allotted “fate”. The use thereof for division of land and booty from conquerors appears to have lived on in the ancient Near East. It is recorded that when Mohammed raided Khaybar he himself set apart arrows for all parts, first a fifth of the share – as the Quran demands in Surah (8:41) – is set aside for community purposes of the general house of Islam, with the rest being further subdivided among the warriors and aides (Silverstein, 2010, p. 428). It can therefore be said that the institution of the divisory lot had stayed alive for millennia and the use of arrows very likely remained common practice.

We can now trace all objects of thought surrounding the casting of lots within the Abrahamic tradition. From its original Mesopotamian source, over its literal manifestation in Judaism, as well as all the pagan influences that led up to the creation of Christianity and Islam that have ultimately influenced broad human thought for millennia. We know of casting lots as a practical use for selection and distribution, a common legal institution, a divine concept of fate, a source of superstition for individual inquiries, and only a very late and marginal association of it with gambling. Most importantly among the grand Abrahamic narrative is the use of divination or “magic” as a term to distinguish one’s culture from another. We can attest that – outside of the Christian realm – finer brushes³¹ had indeed been applied within the Abrahamic debate to distinguish between various applications for the underlying cultural technique of casting lots. Ultimately this debate revolves around when to use one’s own AGENCY to make decisions and when to outsource them to the AGENCY of God.

Lastly, we will compare the Hindu cultural realm to the Abrahamic one.

³¹ As was the initial intention of research for this thesis as written in the introduction on page 1.

DIVINE PLAY

The archeological instance that 6-sided dice did not significantly spread westward of Mesopotamia in pre-literal times – only eastward (see p.65) – turned out to be profound a recurring theme throughout the millennia of an ever-growing Hindu mythology. The concept of Leela, divine play, would significantly shape Hindu spiritual and philosophical concepts. The Hindu stories concerning chance, dice and gambling are briefly summed up here, since they represent an entirely different development from the divisory lot west of Mesopotamia.

The Hindu word for dice is “Pāśaka” (पाशक), but division of property by lot does not appear to be recorded in Hinduism along with the lack of an ancient word that incorporates the concept of a “lot” as in an object of random decision making as well as a portion and fate, in the same way it is used in cultures emerging west of Mesopotamia. However, “Vibhāga” (विभाग) refers to partition as in “dividing shares” with “bhāga” (भाग) meaning “portion”, “share”, but also “divine fortune” or “fate”. The Bhāgavad Gita is also the most important chapter of the Mahabharata, concerning moral and destiny in Hinduism, where Krishna encourages the hero Arjuna not to run from his destiny since it would plague him eternally with guilt but to accept every challenge presented with glee – even if it is war. The prefix “Vibh-“ (विभ-) on the other hand means “division” or “distribution” and it is also found in the fruit “Vibhitaka” (विभीतक) whose seeds are said to be the origin of dice in the Rig Veda.

While sea trade between Mesopotamia and the Indus valley (modern day Pakistan) culture had existed, it had ceased along with the Indus valley culture where findings of cubic clay dice date to around 2500 BCE (Kenoyer, 1998). Part of its people had migrated further east to grow into the Vedic culture (c. 1500–500 BCE) which marks a transformative era in Indian history, spanning the late Bronze and early Iron Ages leading to literacy. It is characterized by the composition of the Vedas in the northern Indian subcontinent, between the decline of the Indus Valley Civilization and the emergence of urban centers in the Ganges Plain around 600 BCE. Within the four Vedas – compilations of hymns and poetry – references to gambling and dice are found in two: The earliest Rig Veda and the latest Atharva Vedas. They provide very contrasting insights into their role in Vedic society of different stages from being condemned to being praised.

THE RIG VEDA – A CAUTIONARY PERSPECTIVE

The Rig Veda is the oldest, dating to around 1500–1100 BCE, when Vedic society was still semi-nomadic. It contains several hymns referencing dice, notably Hymn XXXIV (“Dice, etc.”) in the Fifth Book. It is especially noteworthy since most of the hundreds of hymns are directed towards a deity, like Agni or Varuna, with only a rare few hymns focusing on specific topics, like in this case dice, which are described as having “sprung from tall trees on windy heights” referencing the Vibhitaka seeds. Dice are seen as sources of both joy and destruction and gambling is portrayed as a social ill with moral and family consequences. The hymn details the impact of gambling addiction, alienating men from their families, and reducing kings to servitude: “The King himself pays homage and reveres them.” (Hymn LXXXVI) links dice with sin, comparable to anger and wine, urging piety and labor over gambling: “Play not with dice; cultivate thy cornland.” Other hymns, such as Hymn XXVII and Hymn CXTII tell of warriors engaging in drinking soma and playing dice, which are associated with divine horses, symbolizing their chaotic and uncontrollable nature only the brave can handle. All references were taken from the translated *The hymns of the Rigveda* (Griffith, 1896).

THE ATHARVA VEDA – THE GLORY OF DICE

The Atharva Veda, composed around 1000–800 BCE during the settled Ganges Valley civilization, offers a strikingly different portrayal of gambling. Dice are no longer merely symbols of sin but are integrated into prayers and rituals, reflecting their normalization in society. Gambling is linked to success, prosperity and even royal power, as seen in charms like VI, 38 (“Prayer for Lustre and Power”) and VII, 50 (“Prayer for Success at Dice”). Dice are praised alongside tigers, elephants and gold, highlighting their elevated status. IV, 38 and VII, 50 invoke Apsaras (celestial nymphs) towards dice, with specific deities invoked for gambling. A stark contrast to the Rig Veda. Simultaneously, dice appear in imprecations against sorcery, such as IV, 17 and V, 31, suggesting that gambling’s rise also invited fears of misuse or misfortune. This shift indicates a societal evolution: Gambling moved from being viewed as a vice to a culturally accepted practice, even linked to divine favor and success. It is as if an early Fortuna cult had struck the Ganges Valley civilization in a transformation from a semi-nomadic to a settled, wealth-driven civilization. All references were taken from the translation of Bloomfield (1897).

THE MAHABHARATA – CHANCE, HONOR, AND DESTINY

The *Mahabharata* is among Hinduism's greatest epics and spans more than 2.5 million words³² and within it the caution as well as the glory of dice merge. The epic narrates the feud between the virtuous Pandavas and their deceitful cousins, the Kauravas, culminating in an epic war. At its heart lies the fateful dice game, which Huizinga describes as pivotal in *Homo Ludens* (Huizinga, 1955, p.57). However, Huizinga mostly focuses on the erection of the dice hall and not on the actual dice game and its meaning.

When the pivotal dice game of the epic eventually occurred, Shakuni invited Yudhisthira of the righteous Pandavas to play. Yudhisthira asked him why he would engage in such deceitful practices, claiming it had no “kshatriya”, warrior honor. But Shakuni's argument strikes a chord with the warrior code by telling him that “Victory in gambling is no less honorable than in combat.” to which the warrior code of Yudhisthira has him reply, “Since you have challenged me, I cannot withdraw.” (Ganguli, 1883, Book 2, XLVIII). Huizinga accuses the Kauravas of cheating (Huizinga, 1955, p. 52) but it can be merely described as deceitful, which could be well understood as “bluffing” as Shakuni is said to be skilled at dice, so knowing that he would win could easily be due to his confidence. However, the Mahabharata portrays Shakuni as evil while Yudhistira, who gets lost in the game, as virtuous because he does not give up although he knows that he has no chance of winning. Huizinga pointed out that the Sanskrit word “dyutam” merges the meaning of fighting and dicing (Huizinga, 1955, p.57) but more importantly Shakuni actually brought both AGÔN and ALEA on eye level with the core understanding of LUDUS, arguing that – like in any contest – playing with dice is no different than competing with swords because both follow an inherent „desire for being victorious“ (Ganguli, 1883, Book 2, XLVIII).

Yudhisthira, completely losing himself in the game, gradually increased the stakes until he had lost the entire empire. He then bets his brothers and ultimately himself into slavery. At the very end he even bets Draupadi, the common wife of all the five brothers. Upon hearing this she protests that he was not technically allowed to place her as a bet, since he had already

³² Ganguli, K. M. (1883–1896). *The Mahabharata of Krishna-Dwaipayana Vyasa*. Retrieved (2025, February 6th) from <https://www.wisdomlib.org/hinduism/book/the-mahabharata-mohan>

lost himself to servitude prior to that, therefore having no AGENCY left to make any further bets (LXVI). Draupadi convinces the blind king Dhritarashtra to restore their freedom and with Krishna's help even has all the wealth returned. Shakuni protests, but then simply challenges Yudhishthira to a second game of dice leading to the exact same result. The Pandavas would now be sent into 13 years of exile, eventually setting the stage for the final battle of return (LXXV – LXXVII).

During their exile with countless adventures, the Pandavas hear a familiar story of Nala and Damayanti. Nala, both a virtuous king as well as skilled in dice, gambles away his kingdom to his brother Pushkara just like Yudhishthira had done to Shakuni, ignoring the pleas of his wife Damayanti. Standing by him in absolute loyalty – but only having his clothes left – they both flee into the woods together. When looking for food by hunting golden birds, the birds mock him by stealing his last clothes and reveal themselves as dice and being instruments of Kali, a goddess of sin, who had made him obsessed with gambling. Therefore, only after having lost absolutely everything, the dice left him. Damayanti's loyalty does not match Nala's shame, who abandons her at night (Book 3, LII – LXXIX).

While getting caught in a forest fire Nala encounters a snake who asks to be saved. In return the snake later instructs Nala to learn the art of dice from King Rituparna in exchange for teaching his men charioteering. King Rituparna predicts the exact number of leaves and fruit on a Vibhitaka tree by only analyzing two twigs. Nala then cuts down the tree and spends the whole night counting to find out that he was correct. Afterwards he learned the wisdom of dice from him, or as Ian Hacking described it, the knowledge of probability (Hacking, 1975, p. 7). "Know that I am proficient at dice besides being versed in numbers." states the translation of Ganguli (1883, Book 3, LXXII)

It should show that Nala's newfound mastery ensured his victory. This time it was praised that he got the empire back from Pushkara without shedding a drop of blood. His virtue is shown as he spares Pushkara and returns his part of wealth to him. It embodies a triumph of self-control, moral and reason over compulsion and vengeance.

THE DICE GAME IN THE SIVA PURANA

Though only a small part of the vast Hindu corpus and misattributed to the *Mahabharata* by Huizinga (1955, p.57), the dice game in the *Siva Purana* illustrates the dynamics between Shiva and Parvati, emphasizing themes of attraction, power, and gender roles.

The divine couple is convinced to play dice by the servant Narada, claiming it to be more fun than making love. After some concerns they eventually become completely absorbed and also play in deceitful ways (which could be bluffing as part of the game). Parvati loses at first and becomes angry, which turns Siva on sexually. One time she had wagered and lost some kisses to him but calmed him down by reminding him that the terms also included a grace period of a hundred days and nights. Siva responded by rapidly blinking his eyes, and with each blink a day went by. He was apparently in control of time but not of chance and his ascetic patience was heavily challenged during this game. Later Parvati wins and Siva shows to be a very bad loser, refusing to hand over his stakes. He is reluctant to abide by the rules and maintains to teach Parvati the wisdom that a game and its outcomes are only an illusion (Maya). The servants even approach Parvati to tell her that she is only a woman and should not upset Lord Siva. But she laughs, refuses, and keeps on playing and winning. Later Parvati's winning streak strips him down to his underwear, embarrassing him and all servants around him. Siva sends everyone away in anger, wandering off into the wild, claiming a need to meditate alone. Parvati's friends advise to forgive and run after him, with her refusing since she was playing for fun and won fairly without being a spoilsport. Eventually she still longs for him and changes shape³³ but continuously puts his impatience to test by saying that she is only looking for the highest God known for his self-control, which he clearly lacks. The story is excerpted from Handelman & Shulman (1997).

In both the *Mahabharata*³⁴ and the *Puranas*, women demonstrate to know and honor the rules of games. Yet, like Fortuna, the female part in connection to chaos and chance, both uncontrollable yet irresistible, is a common theme across cultures, with divine will being attributed to male forces like Indra or Zeus, even when lacking all self-control.

³³ Parvati shows traits that are attributed to the nymphic Apsaras, who are said to be of incredible beauty with the ability to shift shapes. They are also invoked in the Vedas for "prayers at dice" as mentioned on p. 100.

³⁴ As displayed on page 101.

SUMMARY OF HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

The earliest written documents of Mesopotamia describe casting lots for legal practices like dividing property, the assignment of duties and the election of officials. There is no sign of casting lots having been a divine ritual but to the contrary a profane one, most likely adopted as established cultural techniques of communal trust by egalitarian tribes of hunters making pre-literal people equal under the lot, before making literal people equal under the law.

Westwards of Mesopotamia the use of casting lots spread mostly as its institutional form but would gain divine status with many leaders casting lots to guide grand communal decisions. Exemplified by the mysterious Ephod, rituals were designed to reduce as much human AGENCY and manipulation. The Hebrew Tanakh represents the media revolution of an established phonetic alphabet that allowed for more elaborate expressions of thought and binding contracts, slowly fading out the institution of casting lots. Spinning philosophical ideas about fate and chance, the Greeks would deify chance in the form of Tyche, the precursor of Fortuna. She would become an all-powerful Roman female God of randomness who would eventually be toppled by a male God of Christian determinism.

The creation of the Christian God in seeing prophecy within a random pattern of Old Jewish scripture shows the profound impact literacy had on human thought, which was excelled by the new format of bound books, whose pages could be picked at random. “Klēros”, the Greek word for lot evolved from an object of choosing into theologically “chosen people”, clerics, who would base their power on scripture. While the act of casting lots could not be profaned it was eventually declared a pagan practice of divination to separate itself from its cultural roots. Only around the 6th century and the creation of Islam would gambling become a matter of discussion within the Abrahamic realm but would remain secondary to maintaining an authority on interpreting scripture and fighting the idea of randomness.

In stark contrast the Indian realm used cubical dice for games long before literacy, which shows both in its mythology as well as in its linguistic roots. The use of dice for playing and gambling was not only condemned but also glorified. Dice in combination with gambling is a much more prevalent theme and its mythology shows a strong code of honor of sticking to rules and social contracts, while developing a different spiritual world of divine play.

CONCLUSION

This thesis introduces the idea that an “aleatory culture” preceded a literary culture as an archaic play element of culture (Huizinga, 1955). Casting lots has probably grown out of a playful act to artificially produce uncertainty by forming mutual and ultimately binding rules upheld in SACRED EARNEST regardless of language. It corrects Roger Caillois, who believed that chance does not possess much institutional value. Instead, chance proved to be of enormous civilizing value to generate fair and unbiased decisions. This thesis therefore proposes that mutually giving up AGENCY to externalize decisions evolved into concepts of higher powers and God.

A common ritual can forge a strong feeling of *communitas* (Turner, 1969) and a common container making all participants equal under the power of the lot. Using containers among gatherer societies provided means of hiding information to make unbiased decisions in egalitarian communities of cooperation. The playful use of arrows besides its function to hunt is argued to be one of the most ancient uses of sortition to divide spoils, hence giving the word lot the secondary meaning of “share”. Whether for exclusive selection or distributive sortition, decorative markings on arrows can make them distinguishable from one another and points to ownership.

Many playful uses would develop out of using long sticks with or without quivers, also for divinatory purposes like the Chinese I Ching, which represents an archetype of cleromancy that also remained a living cultural institution. But it is imperative to point out the need for an interpretative stage like writing or abstract symbols across the documented practices of cleromancy, while lots as well as numerals predate the invention of symbols and scripture.

Unique lots mostly require an additional container, while poly lots like astragals and dice along with binary ones are different in that regard, combining several choices within a single object. Their individual sides were primarily assigned numerals. These numeral lots would find their primary application for playing games among settled societies. Cubical dice emerged and spread in India long before scripture, making it a much more integral part of its mythology with the concept divine play (*Leela*) forming much of its spiritual landscape and very different concepts concerning chance and fate compared to the cultures west of Mesopotamia where the practice of casting lots played a much more fundamental role. In other words, different objects create different objects of thought.

It is argued that with the division of immovable property like land among early agrarian empires of Mesopotamia, the division by lot not only came to be associated with “share” but also “fate” since the allotment of the quality of one’s inheritance could massively influence the life of generations to come. The working of these inheritance laws is well documented while the early myths from Mesopotamia represent the Gods as very anthropomorphic landowners with newly established hierarchies. These earliest written documents of humankind describe the three primal Mesopotamian Gods casting lots to divide the (known) universe. This is also found 1000 years later in the *Iliad*, but the Greeks, with their superior alphabet, would then conceptualize what that force was that even the highest Gods did not control, with the primal deity of chance, Tyche, being a precursor of the Roman Fortuna.

Pre-literal people were equal under the lot, before literal people became equal under the law, and it is exactly this transformation that can be observed in the Hebrew Tanakh, moving from mythology to history with a revolutionary alphabet of only 22 letters. The numerous mentions of casting lots in the Hebrew Tanakh can be mostly reconstructed as a standard legal practice of declaring ownership and assigning public mandates common to the ancient Near East, as well as for making unbiased communal decisions like going to war and selecting battalions. This had reached divine status accompanied by high ritual like the Urim and Thummim and has also been documented by Herodotus among other cultures at this stage in history. Superstitious use of casting lots had also been documented but mostly developed as a playful outlier phenomenon compared from these institutional forms.

The organization of societies with the justice of randomness was replaced by a media revolution with trust in scripture and new theological elites. Whether it was the discontinued use of the Urim and Thummim of the Hebrew priesthood after the destruction of the first temple and the rise of the Rabbinic class of scribes, or the toppling of the all-powerful Fortuna cult in Rome with the replacement of the Christian deterministic God.

The use of the term “cleromancy” in association with casting lots in general stems from the rise of the power of the Christian church and its effort to ban the practice altogether as pagan (Greek and Roman) practices, but also to disassociate itself from its Jewish roots. Most of its original legal uses had been forgotten and its use limited to only the highest spiritual necessities of divine guidance. Any profane use would now upset the sovereignty of God, while the word for lot “*klēros*” was transformed from an object of choosing into “chosen people”, clerics.

Anything labeled “divination” was only analyzed during Renaissance times after 1000 years of philosophical suppression. But the “-mancy” terminology was adopted by Renaissance rationalists, 19th century occultists and early anthropologists alike, giving linguistic features of both ridiculing a practice, as well as being suitable for categorizing and appearing scientific. The latter use stuck within academic discourse but lacked the ability to differentiate the objects from the methods and intentions used. The wide use of the word “cleromancy” has therefore stuck within academic discourse, but the analysis of underlying cultural techniques provides much better insights.

As with most cultural techniques, the ideas – or objects of thought - of randomness and chance were only formulated long after it was practiced and already cultivated. As metaphysical ideas, chaos, luck, chance, fate and randomness would undergo millennia of literal conceptualization, it remains an intellectual journey that is far from finished. This thesis therefore recommends a general clarity in definitions on different types of uncertainty - like randomness and chance - for further academic discourse.

Final remarks:

I hope that this thesis can add to the sharpening of a lens of game studies by providing a toolset that is also applicable and beneficial outside of its own domain, whether it be history, religious studies, or philosophical discourse. Analyzing AGENCY, measurable feedback and interactions of participants can quickly map out differences, similarities, and possibilities.

A finer brush concerning clarity on different types of uncertainty, chance, probability, randomness, chaos, luck and fate, along with a morally neutral view on gambling and the evaluation of risk would be beneficial for a common academic discourse.

Further research concerning different animals and their possible use of chance as well as different cultural practices and deifications of chance would be favorable to evaluate what is necessary for an “aleatory” development.

GLOSSARY

AGENCY – The capacity of a player to make meaningful choices that impact the outcome. Strong AGENCY in a game means players feel their actions have consequences, whether through narrative decisions, mechanics, or emergent gameplay.

AGÔN – The first of Caillois’ four categories of play. Competitive games where skill and strategy determine the outcome and victory is based on merit. Examples include chess, sports, and esports. (p. 13)

ALEA – The second of Caillois’ categories. Games of chance where the outcome is determined by randomness rather than skill. ALEA contrasts AGÔN, as the player’s actions have no effect on results. Examples include roulette, slot machines, and dice games. (p. 13)

Chance – A quantifiable outcome occurring at **random**. This word has undergone most of an evolution since the theory of **probability**, as its etymology suggests it being the idea of something happening accidentally. It is the cultivated idea subject to this thesis. (p. 26)

Chaos – A lack of order. Chaos is not quantifiable like a random shape. (p. 26)

Gambling – A form of play that involves wagering or staking something of value (e.g., money, items) on an uncertain outcome, not necessarily via ALEA. Gambling can be analyzed in terms of risk and reward. (p. 18)

ILINX – The final category in Caillois’ four categories, referring to play that creates a sense of vertigo or dizziness. Examples include roller coasters, extreme sports, or virtual reality experiences that disorient the player. (p. 13)

Luck – A personal experience of fortune and reward closely linked to dopamine, whether unexpected or anticipated, but not stemming from one’s own actions. (p. 26)

LUDUS – The structured, rule-based counterpart to PAIDIA, also defined by Caillois. LUDUS emphasizes challenge, clear objectives, and formalized rules. Most traditional board games and competitive video games fall under this category. (p. 12)

MEANINGFUL PLAY – A concept from game design theory (Salen & Zimmerman) that describes play where player actions have discernible and integrated outcomes, making the experience engaging and rewarding. (p. 15)

MIMICRY – The third category of play by Caillois that involves role-playing, make-believe, or simulation. This includes activities like acting, cosplay, or games where players assume fictional roles. (p. 13)

PAIDIA – A term by Roger Caillois to describe free, spontaneous, and unstructured play. It contrasts with **LUDUS**, as it is more exploratory and improvisational rather than rule-bound. Examples include sandbox games or children's imaginative play. (p. 12)

Probability – A mathematical framework of measuring chances. (p. 28)

Randomness – A lack of predictability in events, patterns, or outcomes. The etymological root of "speed" suggests to quickly come out of nowhere but also spinning a teetotum or a wheel of fortune. Randomness remains unpredictable and unquantifiable but does not necessarily stem from **chaos** and can exist within a system. (p. 26)

Risk – Implies a stake that can be lost (or won), anticipating a good or bad outcome. It seeks to estimate the odds based on known factors. (p. 26)

SACRED EARNEST – A concept of Johan Huizinga (1938) referring to a state in play where players taking it absolutely seriously to uphold a common play world, whether being a common set of rules or narrative - despite knowing it is "just a game". It's cultural adaptations into real life would be what he called the play element of culture (p. 10)

Uncertainty – A lack of knowledge, being the opposite of certainty. (p. 26)

LITERATURE LIST

- Aquinas, T. (1266–1273). *The "Summa theologica" of St. Thomas Aquinas*. Burns, Oates & Washburne.
- Adams, D. (1979). *The hitchhiker's guide to the galaxy*. Pan Books.
- Alfonso X. (1283). *Libro de los juegos* [The book of games]. (M. L. D. Núñez, Trans.). Ediciones Akal. (Original work published 1283).
- Agrippa, H. C. (2021). *Three books of occult philosophy* (E. Purdue, Trans.). Inner Traditions. (Original work published 1533).
- Amandry, P. (1950). *La mantique apollinienne à Delphes: Essai sur le fonctionnement de l'oracle*. E. de Boccard.
- Augustine of Hippo. (1991). *Confessions* (H. Chadwick, Trans.). Oxford University Press. (Original work published ca. 397 CE).
- Augustine of Hippo. (2009). *The city of God* (H. Bettenson, Trans.). Hendrickson Publishers. (Original work published ca. 426 CE).
- Avedon, E. M., & Sutton-Smith, B. (1971). *The study of games*. Wiley.
- Bailey, N. (1727). *An universal etymological English dictionary*. T. Cox.
- Barnes, M. P. (2012). *Runes: A handbook*. Boydell Press.
- Barrett, J. (2004). *Why would anyone believe in God?* AltaMira Press.
- Barrett, C. K. (2004). *The New Testament background: Selected documents*. Harper & Row.
- Beale, G. K. (2012). *Handbook on the New Testament use of the Old Testament*. Baker Academic.
- Beard, M., North, J., & Price, S. (1998). *Religions of Rome: Volume I, A history*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bell, R. C. (1960). *Board and table games from many civilizations* (p. 23). Oxford University Press.
- Ben-Sasson, H. H. (1976). *A history of the Jewish people*. Harvard University Press.
- Bloomfield, M. (1897). *The Atharva-Veda*. Clarendon Press.
- Browne, T. (1646). *Pseudodoxia epidemica: Or, enquiries into very many received tenets, and commonly presumed truths*. Printed by S. Griffin for Edward Dodsley.
- Buchholz, L. (2013). *Identifying the oracular sortes of Italy*. *Acta Instituti Romani Finlandiae*, Vol. 40. University of Helsinki.
- Budge, E. A. W. (Trans.). (1895). *The Egyptian Book of the Dead: The Book of Going Forth by Day*. Dover Publications.

- Caillois, R. (2001). *Man, play and games* (M. Barash, Trans.). University of Illinois Press. (Original work published 1958).
- Cardano, G. (1663). *Liber de ludo aleae* [The book on games of chance]. In C. Spon (Ed.), *Opera omnia* (Vol. 1, pp. 263–278). Lyons, France. (Original work written ca. 1564).
- Cantlon, J. F., & Brannon, E. M. (2006). Shared system for ordering small and large numbers in monkeys and humans. *Psychological Science*.
- Cicero, M. T. (1923). *De Divinatione* (W. A. Falconer, Trans.). Loeb Classical Library. Harvard University Press. (Original work written ca. 44 BCE). Retrieved (2025, February 6th) from https://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/e/roman/texts/cicero/de_divinatione/2*.html
- Culin, S. (1895). *Korean Games, With Notes on the Corresponding Games of China and Japan*. University of Pennsylvania.
- Culin, S. (1907). *Games of the North American Indians*. Bureau of American Ethnology.
- David, F. N. (1962). *Games, gods and gambling*. Griffin.
- Davidson, H. R. Ellis, (1988) *Gods and Myths of Northern Europe*. Penguin.
- Epstein, R. (2009). *The theory of gambling and statistical logic*. Academic Press.
- Encyclopædia Britannica. (n.d.). Divination. In *Encyclopædia Britannica Online*. Retrieved February 3, 2025, from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/divination>
- Erekens, J. W., & de Voogt, A. (2022). Why are Roman-period dice asymmetrical? An experimental and quantitative approach. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 14(7), 134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-022-01599-y>
- Erkes, E. (1945). *The significance of the I Ching as a book of divination*. Leipzig University.
- Finkelstein, I., & Silberman, N. A. (2001). *The Bible unearthed: Archaeology's new vision of ancient Israel and the origin of its sacred texts*. Free Press.
- Finley, M. I. (1983). *Politics in the ancient world*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gamble, H. (1995). *Books and readers in the early church: A history of early Christian texts*. Yale University Press.
- Ganguli, K. M. (1883–1896). *The Mahabharata of Krishna-Dwaipayana Vyasa*. Retrieved (2025, February 6th) from <https://www.wisdomlib.org/hinduism/book/the-mahabharata-mohan>
- Gataker, T. (1619). *Of the nature of using lots*.
- Goody, J. (1986). *The logic of writing and the organization of society*. Cambridge University Press.
- Griffith, R. T. H. (1896). *The hymns of the Rigveda* (2nd ed.). E.J. Lazarus & Co.

- Haddow, S. D. (Ed.). (2015). *Çatalhöyük 2015 Archive Report*. Çatalhöyük Research Project. https://www.catalhoyuk.com/sites/default/files/media/pdf/Archive_Report_2015.pdf
- Hacking, I. (1975). *The emergence of probability. Second edition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hallo, W. W. (1983). *The first Purim*. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/the-first-purim>
- Hays, R. B. (1989). *Echoes of scripture in the letters of Paul*. Yale University Press.
- Hefele, C. J. (1895). *A history of the councils of the church* (Vol. 3). T&T Clark.
- Heinrich, B., & Smolker, R. (1991). Play in common ravens (*Corvus corax*). *Journal of Comparative Psychology*, 105(3), 295-302. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7036.105.3.295>
- Herodotus. (1920). *The histories* (A. D. Godley, Trans.). Harvard University Press. (Original work composed ca. 5th century BCE).
- Heinevetter, F. (1912). *Würfel- und Buchstabenorakel in Griechenland und Kleinasien*. Koebner.
- Huizinga, J. (1955). *Homo ludens: A study of the play-element in culture* (R. F. C. Hull, Trans.). Beacon Press. (Original work published 1938).
- Hurtado, L. (2006). *The earliest Christian artifacts: Manuscripts and Christian origins*. Eerdmans.
- Ibn al-Kalbi, H. (c. 9th century; 1952). *The book of idols: Being a translation from the Arabic of the Kitāb al-Aṣnām* (N. A. Faris, Trans.). Princeton University Press.
- Ibn Hisham. (2002). *The life of Muhammad: A translation of Ishaq's Sirat Rasul Allah* (A. Guillaume, Trans.). Oxford University Press. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/TheLifeOfMohammedGuillaume>
- Jackson, D. A. (2020). The paradox of divination: A biblical examination of divination in ancient Israel.
- Jerome. (1994). *Commentary on Numbers* (Translated by A. Cain). The Catholic University of America Press.
- Johnston, S. I. (2008). *Ancient Greek divination*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- John of Damascus. (c. 733 CE). *Exposition of the Orthodox Faith* (F. H. Chase, Trans.). Harvard University Press, 1958. (Original work published c. 733 CE).
- Kahneman, D., Slovic, P., & Tversky, A. (Eds.). (1977). *Foundations of measurement* (Vol. 1). Academic Press.
- Kahneman, D., Slovic, P., & Tversky, A. (Eds.). (1982). *Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and biases*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979). Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2), 263-291.
- Kapp, K. M. (2012). *The gamification of learning and instruction: Game-based methods and strategies for training and education*. Pfeiffer.

- Kenoyer, J. M. (1998). *Ancient cities of the Indus Valley Civilization*. Oxford University Press.
- Kitz, A. M. (1997). The plural form of 'Ūrîm and Tummîm. *Journal of Biblical Literature*, 116(3), 401–410.
- Kitz, A. M. (2000). Undivided inheritance and lot casting in the book of Joshua. *Journal of Biblical Literature*, 119(4), 601–618.
- Lamberg-Karlovsky, C. C. (1972). Trade mechanisms in Indus-Mesopotamian interrelations. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 92(2), 222-229.
- Le Guin, U. K. (1988). The carrier-bag theory of fiction. In D. Du Pont (Ed.), *Women of vision* (pp. 1–12). St. Martin's Press.
- Lévi, É. (2001). *The history of magic* (A. E. Waite, Trans.). Weiser Books. (Original work published 1860).
- Lewin, A. (2005). *The archaeology of ancient Judea and Palestine*. Getty Publications.
- Li, B. (2003). *The collected poems of Li Bai* (J. C. H. Wu, Trans.). Columbia University Press.
- Lindblom, J. (1975). *The emergence of probability*. Cambridge University Press.
- Milman, H. H. (1890). *The Mahabharata* (Vol. 1). Kegan Paul, Trench & Co.
- McCoy, A. N., & Platt, M. L. (2005). Risk-sensitive neurons in macaque posterior cingulate cortex. *Nature Neuroscience*.
- Metropolitan Museum of Art. (2004, October; revised 2018, January). *Board games from ancient Egypt and the Near East*. In Heilbrunn Timeline of Art History. Retrieved February 6, 2025, from <https://www.metmuseum.org/essays/board-games-from-ancient-egypt-and-the-near-east>
- Montague, R. P., King-Casas, B., & Cohen, J. D. (2005). Neural economics and decision making: Risk and reward. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, 28, 363-398.
- Milman, H. H. (1890). *The Mahabharata* (Vol. 1). Kegan Paul, Trench & Co.
- Needham, J. (2008). *Science and civilisation in China* (Vol. 7). Cambridge University Press.
- Neusner, J. (1987). *The theology of the Talmud*. University of Chicago Press.
- New International Version. (2011). *The Holy Bible, New International Version*. Zondervan.
- Ong, W. J. (1982). *Orality and literacy: The technologizing of the word*. Methuen.
- Ovid. (2000). *Fasti* (A. D. Melville, Trans.). Oxford University Press. (Original work published c. 8 CE)
- Parlett, D. (2018). *The Oxford history of board games* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Pankenier, D. (2013). *Astrology and cosmology in early China: Conforming earth to heaven*. Cambridge University Press.

- Payne, J. B. (1973). *Encyclopedia of biblical prophecy: The complete guide to scriptural predictions and their fulfillment*. Baker Book House.
- Piccione, P. A. (1980). In search of the meaning of senet. *Archaeology*, 33(4), 55–58.
- Plato. (c. 380 BCE/2004). *Republic* (C. D. C. Reeve, Trans.). Hackett Publishing.
- Pindar. (c. 470 BCE/1990). *Olympian Ode 10* (A. M. N. M. Fletcher, Trans.). In *The Odes of Pindar* (pp. 23–24). Harvard University Press.
- Procyk, E., Tanaka, Y. L., & Joseph, J. P. (2000). Anterior cingulate activity during routine and non-routine sequential behaviors in macaques. *Nature Neuroscience*.
- Reeves, J. (2015). The secularization of chance: Towards understanding the impact of the probability revolution on Christian belief in divine providence. *Zygon*, 50(3), 604–620.
- Roberts, C. H., & Skeat, T. C. (1983). *The birth of the codex*. Oxford University Press.
- Sahih International. (1997). *The Qur'an: English Meanings and Notes*. Abul-Qasim Publishing.
- Schädler, U. (1996). Spielen mit Astragalen. *Archäologischer Anzeiger*, 1, 61–73.
- Schwartz, D. G. (2006). *Roll the bones: The history of gambling*. Gotham Books.
- Skinner, B. F. (1948). Superstitions in pigeons. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 38(2), 168–172.
- Skinner, B. F., & Ferster, C. B. (1957). *Schedules of reinforcement*. Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Siegert, B. (2020). Attached: The object and the collective. In J. Dünne, K. Fehring, K. Kuhn, & W. Struck (Eds.), *Cultural techniques: Assembling spaces, texts & collectives* (pp. 131–140). De Gruyter.
- Silverstein, A., & Crone, P. (2010). The ancient Near East and Islam: The case of lot-casting. *Journal of Semitic Studies*, 55(2), 423–450. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jss/fgq007>
- Smith, R. J. (2012). *The I Ching: A biography*. Princeton University Press.
- Speiser, E. A. (1935). Tepe Gawra: A prehistoric site in northern Iraq. *American Journal of Archaeology*, 39(3), 300–311.
- Suetonius. (c. 121 CE/2001). *The Lives of the Caesars* (J. C. Rolfe, Trans.). Harvard University Press.
- Tacitus. (1964). *Germania* (H. Mattingly, Trans.). London: Penguin Books. (Original work published ca. 98 CE).
- Tertullian. (1970). *De Spectaculis* (C. D. Yonge, Trans.). In *Ante-Nicene Fathers* (Vol. 3, pp. 55–65). Hendrickson Publishers. (Original work published ca. 200 CE).
- Tibaldini, M. (2023). Astragalomanteion, Sortes Sanctorum, Sortes Monacenses: Stratification of gaming practices and cultural traditions from early antiquity to the Middle Ages. *Mirabilia*, 37(2), 9–60.

Toomey, D. (2023). *The kingdom of play: What games teach us about the nature of play, the brain, and humanity*. Goldmann.

Turner, V. (1969). *The ritual process: Structure and anti-structure*. Aldine Publishing.

Von Neumann, J., & Morgenstern, O. (1944). *Theory of games and economic behavior*. Princeton University Press.

Weatherford, J. (1997). *The history of money*. Three Rivers Press.

Woolley, C. L. (1934). *Ur: The royal cemetery*. The University Press.

Yang, B. (2019). *Cowrie Shells and Cowrie Money: A Global History*. Routledge.

GAMES MENTIONED

Hasbro. (1957). *Risk* [Board game]. Hasbro.

Milton Bradley Co. (1943). *Chutes & Ladders* [Board game]. Milton Bradley.

DIAGRAMS

Diagram 1: Framework of this thesis

Source: Own representation

Diagram 2: Juxtaposition of play – divination – decision making

Source: Own representation

TABLES

Table 1: Play categories after Roger Caillois

Source: Own representation based on (Caillois, 2001, p. 36)

Table 2: Lot categories

Source: Own representation

Table 3: Sub-categories of unique lots

Source: Own representation

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Retrieved from: Culin, S. (1895). *Korean Games, With Notes on the Corresponding Games of China and Japan*. University of Pennsylvania.
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Piccione, P. A. (1980). In search of the meaning of senet. *Archaeology*, 33(4), 55–58.
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Retrieved on February 6th, 2025, from:
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Retrieved on February 6th, 2025, from:
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Retrieved on February 6th, 2025, from:
<https://mdc.bidinside.com/fr/lot/61/plaetorius-cestianus-69-av-jc-denier/>
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Retrieved on February 6th, 2025, from:
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tempio_della_fortuna_primigenia_a_Praeneste,_before_1976_-_Archivio_Accademia_delle_Sienze_Torino,_Millon_66_28_396.jpg
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Retrieved on February 6th, 2025, from: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Bibliomancie_-_Tiers_Livre_de_Rabelais_illustr%C3%A9_par_Albert_Robida,_chap._X.jpg
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Source: Own photograph, Ivo Herzl, 2025